

FROM WAR TO PEACE:
**THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY
IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION**

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DECLARATION

I declare that this study is my original work and affirm that to the best of my knowledge, this thesis has not been presented in any other university for examination or for any other purpose. This work forms part of the fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the Degree of Bachelor of Landscape Architecture in the School of Architecture and Building sciences, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology.

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INSPIRATION

“Behold how good and pleasant it is for brethren to dwell together in unity! It is like the precious ointment upon the head that ran down upon the beard, even Aaron’s beard: that went down to the skirts of his garments; as the dew of Hermon, and as the dew that descended upon the mount of Zion: for there the Lord commanded the blessing, even life for evermore.”

(Psalm 133 Vs 1)

“.....Peace is not the absence of conflict; it is the ability to handle conflict by peaceful means....”

By Ronald Reagan

DEDICATION

Specially to: My Mum Becky, Dad Mr. Oremo and siblings Geoffrey, Edna and Erick.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First, I thank the King eternal, most wise, invisible, immortal Almighty God The Ancient of days, for His power and might upon me and my classmates in the period we have been in the university.

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ABSTRACT

At times 'sister communities' may exist in rivalry. From observation, the Kipsigis and Kisii communities of Bomet and Nyamira Counties respectively are an example of such a case. From time in history, rivalry between these two communities has existed majorly due to massive cattle raiding amongst themselves and land conflicts. This rivalry, when chance presents, spurs into extreme violence. The place has been identified as one of the Kenya's hotspots as evident during the 1992 and most recent 2007-2008 clashes period.

These conflicts have directly affected the physical environment so that fragmentation exists between the two communities. This has therefore resulted to the lack of cohesion and thus disintegration between these two groups. Many methods have been used to facilitate peace between these two communities, and this thesis seeks to add to these methods by the use of a greenway network strategy. The study sought to find the status of the green space planning between the two communities, and the levels of interactions as a result of the presence/absence of rivalry. Survey methods entailing the use of random and purposive sampling techniques were carried out. These were enabled by the use of questionnaires that were administered to 3 centres in Bomet and 4 centres in Nyamira Counties, together with focussed group discussions and interview schedules for resource persons.

In general, the research, being informed by the inter-personal tie theory and contact theory found that open spaces have an effect on social cohesion, even from times in history. More findings in line with the recommendations thereof are discussed in the end chapters.

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

1.0 PROBLEM BACKGROUND.

“Proud of our ethnic, cultural and religious diversity and determined to live in peace and unity as one indivisible sovereign nation”, is a preamble statement of The Constitution of Kenya. However into the country’s independence, when unity/oneness is a tool to national development and progress, negative ethnicity, has been the single aspect of diversity that has generated the greatest difficulties in enhancing national cohesion and integration (The Constitution of Kenya, 2010).

Since the transition to multiparty-ism in the 1990s, ethnic violence in Kenya has been part of political strategies to retain or win power (Klopp, 2001). Cycles of aggression and antagonist articulation of ethnic identity of perceived hostile voters have enmeshed grievances over unequal land distribution into political discourses of exclusion (Kamungi, 2009).Increased use of hate speech, intimidation and inability to recover from the cyclic violence has encouraged ethnic balkanization in some areas and institutions.

Kenya has been riddled with conflict and violence throughout its brief history as a nation. (Mara, September 2009)Thus our nation has been termed to be a “divided nation” (NTV Broadcast 21st April 2012) due to the existence of these conflicts.

Plate 1.Women peace race a Sotik-Borabu area (Source; web link)

Plate 2 Violent people behind fence (Source; web link)

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

Peaceful existence between communities would enable the country its activities smoothly. It is a sign of development and prosperity. Civilization cannot progress if there is no peace in the country.

Research has shown that in Kenya some counties are disconnected and an example of this case is Turkana County and West Pokot County (Mnangat, 2011), Bomet and Kisii Counties (Abaya, 2011) among others. This ought not to be case when our country is in a race to achieve the Vision 2030.

National cohesion and integration becomes a necessary tool in our country to be able to achieve its visions, missions and goals. This could only be achieved when all the Kenya's ethnic groups exist with love for each another, in peace and liberty running together for a common objective of building our nation together. (Anthem, 1963).In Kenya and similarly other countries, many measures have been put in place to ensure that there is peace amongst the citizens.This research aims to introduce the idea of greenway design strategy as one of the method that could also be used to achieve peace.

Figure 1.Green moment diagram
Source <http://www.corridor strategy.com>

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Rivalries often exist between neighbouring towns, cities, states or countries.(Phillips,1994) Economic power, political opinions, religious systems culture, universities, schools and other factors can create both positive and negative attitudes, feelings of competition or, and rivalries amongst communities. (Koter & Kulesza, 1999) (Flink C. A. ; Searns Ve., 1993)Several factors have been identified as the source of outbreaks of communal violence among ethnic populations living in close proximity to each other in Kenya. A document by (Ekiru, 2011)and research carried out by Mnangat 2011 show that this is as a result of political instigation , regional disparities, land conflicts, lack of access to water and pasture resources, loss of traditional grazing land, cattle raiding, lack of alternative sources of livelihood, fears of terrorism, harassment, theft and extortion

The Kenya counties of Bomet and Nyamira located in the South West region of Kenya lie in proximity to each other. These two counties are majorly occupied by the Kipsigis and Kisii communities respectively. Owing to the fact that these communities border each other, they happen to share a lot in common – institutions, schools, markets centres, water sources and so on.

Despite of the sharing of amenities, personal experience and research done by others show that these two communities appear to be in constant rivalry (Mbugua, 2009).

Plate 3 Chebilat, shared border centre
(Source: Author)

Plate 4 Border area, shared amenities (Source: Author)

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

Although most of the direct violence ceased after the post-election violence, continuing mistrust and tension has been very apparent for instance at the border market centre where members from each community kept separate selling corners trading only with their community members. Some small business owners also had to close shops if they operated in the perceived “wrong areas”.

As a result of this rivalry, there exists fragmentation between these two communities up to this date evident with most of the residential zones existing a good way off the boundary area, leaving the border zone as an area in which most people go to work i.e in the tea farms, tea collection points and eventually they commute back to their homes.

The border market center Chebilat, together with open spaces located at the border area, are used as battle grounds between the two communities. Narrow corridors and open spaces that with forests and rivers become dangerous zones for the people, especially at night. However, these greenway network components are of great importance to the residents of these two communities. They serve as areas for holding peace meetings, rallies, seminars and campaigns among the two ethnic groups.

As Kenya is looking forward to a devolved system of government, peace resolution measures should be implemented starting from the least levels of governance. The concept here is to act local and in the long run the turnout is a national development tool.

Plate 5 Post- election ruins in the Borabu-Sotik area (Source: web link)

Plate6 Fragmentation between Bomet and Nyamira Counties (Source;author)

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

1.2 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study aims at investigating the potential of greenway network design as a tool to link counties in rivalry as to achieve social cohesion. This is to be achieved through planning and designing of open spaces in a greenway network which have facilities that will bring people from the different groups with different ethnicity values together for social interaction, appreciation of cultural diversity hence promote unity among citizens and consequently the nation as a whole.

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Ultimate Objective- To develop a framework that enhances planning and designing of spaces which promote more interactions by multi-ethnic groups for ultimate social cohesion.

Specific Objectives

To establish the status of greenspace planning between Bomet and Nyamira Counties.

To investigate the presence/absence of rivalry between the two communities hence interaction information.

To describe the relationship between the greenspace planning and social cohesion.

Plate 7 Open space along the border
(Source: Author)

Plate 8 Manmade forest in an open space
(Source: Author)

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

1.4 STUDY ASSUMPTIONS.

Bomet and Nyamira Counties are two neighbouring counties that face ethnic intolerance and therefore pose a good representative of the entire Kenyan neighbouring communities that exist in rivalry with each other.

People from these communities will prefer to meet at the greenway network area than any other place in their communities due to the dynamism of spaces.

1.5 STUDY HYPOTHESES

Null

Open spaces have an effect on social cohesion.

Alternate

Open spaces do not have an effect on social cohesion.

Figure 2 Abstract of dynamism (Source: author)

Figure 3 Model of cohesion(source; author)

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

1.6 STUDY SIGNIFICANCE

Greenway networks are important aspects of any urban or rural area. It is through certain unique elements of the greenway network component that the identities of places are formed. These components (activity nodes, nodes and corridors) form the platform on which human needs are met, where activity nodes are the focal points of activities e.g. market places, institutions etc., nodes are non-linear areas and corridors are linear arrangements of natural areas or elements that can be considered a place or an event.

The three components define the levels of social cohesion of a place or area. Components of representation, redistribution and recognition are key to proper spatial planning are key in enhancing integration and cohesion or the vice versa (Conine, Xiang, Young, & Whitley, 2004).

By a large extent the greenway network will improve social cohesion as it will be a place where people interact thus enhancing the sense of community. It will provide access and linkage between the nodes and patches hence acting as an anchor for revitalizing the two neighbourhoods and building much healthier communities. The creation of international collaboration opportunities, in particular cross-border co-operation, will be as a result of the initiation of the exchange of experiences, information and knowledge between users along the greenway as a result of contact.

Figure 4 linear greenway
(Source; <http://www.wikimedia.org>)

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

This will boost the esteem of these two communities hence uniting them for common goals and objectives, enabling them to build the nation together.

1.7 STUDY JUSTIFICATION

This research is timely as peace needs to prevail in our country between all the ethnic groups.

Revised Version, June 2009. *Standard guidelines and terms of reference for peace structures in Kenya*

(V).The subjective dimension of social cohesion and integration relates to the extent to which the members of a community feel that they are part of both the society and the processes of integration.(National Cohesion and Integration Act,2008)

Chapter two of the Constitution of Kenya calls for the need of National cohesion and integration for instance, in the National values and Heritage with its principles of governance including national unity, social justice, inclusiveness and equity. Its bill of rights provide for equality and freedom from discrimination, guaranteeing the basic economic and social right for all, while encouraging respect for diversity and fostering a sense of belonging. One way of addressing the issue of lack of cohesion is through the promotion and celebration of equality, ethnic and cultural diversities by creating effective interactions and bridging activities such as cultural works, shared spaces, sports and establishing mechanisms for communication and information sharing.

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

This study therefore aims at establishing ways through which the greenway network design can be used as a mechanism to bring people from multi-ethnic and multi-cultural communities together. It is of extreme importance as its findings and proposals could be employed in many areas of this nation to serve for its peace initiatives, revitalisation capabilities, and connectivity between areas, social cohesion and integration purposes, besides other unlisted broad principles.

Figure 5 showing a framework of greenway networks that can facilitate cohesion and other principles. (Source: author)

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1.8 STUDY LIMITATIONS

The study required collection of critical information such that time was a limiting factor. To counter this, early preparations of getting permissions from institutions, and acquiring of interpreters were done.

The study involved an elaborate interviewing people in the study area and collecting information from experts of planning and those in the peace border committee. To avoid any institutional bureaucracies, early preparations and arrangements were made prior.

Negative respondents' attitudes rendered it necessary to consider the use of authority i.e. area chief and a few influential residents in the respective sampled out areas to enable carrying out the research should be done.

Plate 9 Focused group interview with an interpreter

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1.8 STUDY SCOPE

1.8.1 GEOGRAPHICAL SCOPE

The study area will be based at the transition zone between Bomet and Nyamira Counties specifically between Chepilat border market and Borabu area respectively. It is the most appropriate area of this study as the area due to the following reasons;

The area has served as the battle ground at all times of war between the two groups in history .

The area has got varied land uses, activities and typologies therefore records a higher population compared to the other places along the border.

Besides having the majority of its population from the Kipsigis and Kisii community, the area has got other ethnic groups (Kikuyu, Luo, Luhya, Nandi, Marakwet, and Maasai) living there.

Finally, the area hosts the Kisii Highway that increases the livability of the area.

All these pose a myriad of opportunities for the better functionality of the greenway network strategy to achieve ultimate social cohesion.

Map 1 Sotik- Borabu border (Source: Author)

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Map.2 Location of Kenya in the Africa Continental context
Source: www.worldmaps.com

Map 3 Kenya
Source; Survey of Kenya

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Map 4 Location of Bomet and Nyamira counties within the country context
Source: Survey of Kenya

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Map 5 Bomet and Nyamira counties in the context of the South Western region of Kenya
 Source: www.googlemaps.com

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Map 6 Chepilat centre at the border between Kipsigis in Bomet and Kisii in Nyanza
 Source: [www. googlemaps.com](http://www.googlemaps.com)

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1.8.2 THEORETICAL SCOPE

This thesis proposed two theories - The Contact Theory hand in hand with the Theory of Interpersonal Ties to explain that it is possible to enhance social cohesion between the two “sister” communities of Bomet and Nyamira Counties earlier stated that exist in rivalry.

While the contact theory states that inter-group contact can help reduce prejudice, it has with it certain conditions that have to be fulfilled These conditions forming the basis of the this theory include equality in status, pleasure of contact experience between the groups, sharing of common goals and support/promotion by the authority.

If these conditions are not met, then there is no guarantee that change for positive attitude will occur and there is a possibility of an increase in intergroup conflict and prejudice (Bratt, 2002).

On the other hand, the inter-personal ties theory narrows down to the level of individuals nurturing the idea that positive personal interactions are the foundations of all social processes.

Figure 6 Model of open spaces that promote cohesion (Source: author)

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individual's basic personality or self-conception.....,the development and maintenance of myriad attitudes towards the world, the determination and social control of "appropriate behaviour"....., and the maintenance of a "motivational commitment to participate".....Indeed, the intimate face-to-face group is often held to form the critical "primary environment" by which an individual is related to the larger society....." Therefore many researchers and investigators have described in depth about the magnitude of this Inter-personal Ties Theory among individuals/groups as a basis of social cohesion. (Cartwright 1968, Gross & Martin 1952,Lott and Lott 1965)

Research, since the development of the contact theory by Gordon Allport about half a century ago has proven this to be one of the most effective strategies for improving intergroup relations.

The theory It is based on the notion that prejudice often occurs as a result of limited contact between groups hence limited knowledge about the other, it argues that by organising more intergroup contacts these groups will understand their different behaviours, cultural lifestyles, experiences and will therefore create a forum of understanding between the two groups.

The theory assumes that the information acquired through contact is generalized to the whole group and thus negative stereo-typical views are consequently disapproved (Ellison and Powers,1994).

Figure 7 Model of contact hypotheses within a group of interacting communities.(Source; author)

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Moreno and Jennings (1937) argued that social cohesion is indicated by the number of mutual dyadic ties within a group. Festinger (1950) together with other researchers (Frank 1996, Frank & Yasumoto 1998) have treated the density (or relative density) of interpersonal relations in a group as a group-level measure or basis of cohesion.

This study therefore will aim to promote positive social inter-personal and intergroup ties among varied ethnic groups through interactions in the greenway network area first by aiding the formation of a person's self-conception so that he/she may be able to adapt to a myriad of attitudes by different people and hence be able to fit in the larger society. By doing so, these different ethnic groups will develop resistance to the disruptive forces that normally cause rivalry and conflict as such togetherness/cohesiveness is associated with the strength of the strong interpersonal bonds among themselves.

There will be an increase of public interactions as well as sense of unity and more so appreciation and enjoyment through various cultural, economic and social activities established in the open spaces of the greenway network. By doing so the greenway network becomes the most preferable social space at the expense of other meeting areas.

Plate 10 Interpersonal ties theory (Moreno & Jennings, 1937))

Plate 11 Intergroup ties theory (Moreno & Jennings, 1937)

1.9 STUDY ORGANISATION

Chapter 1 includes an introduction or background to the problem, problem statement, and purpose of the study, the objectives, assumptions, significance, justification, scope and finally the limitations of the study.

Chapter 2 features an in depth literature review of the importance of greenway networks, and a critical review of methods and instruments used in previous research studies.

Chapter 3 entails the research methodology. Aspects to be tackled out includes the research approach, research design, research situs, research methods, data collection techniques, sampling technique, program for data collection, data processing, data analysis and presentation, research ethics, work plan and timetable, and the research budgets.

Chapter 4 gives Introduction the history and development of the study area, the legal and institutional frameworks, physiographic and natural conditions of the area and discussions.5

Chapter 5 entails data analysis and discussion.

Chapter 6 entails the theoretical implications, methodological implications, practical implications, general conclusions of the study and finally recommendations for design frameworks and areas for further research.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Features an in depth literature review on greenway networks, studies on cohesion globally and locally and a critical review of methods and instruments used in previous research studies.

2.1. AN UNDERSTANDING OF GREENWAY NETWORKS

Greenways are linear open spaces along natural or artificial corridors such as riverfront, streams, ridge-lines, abandoned railroad right-of-ways, canals or scenic roads (Little, 1990; Smith, 1993; Lindsey, 1999).

Greenway network therefore refers to greenery and interconnected linear open spaces formed by treed streets, waterways and drainage ways around and between areas, at all spatial scales (Little, 1990; Smith, 1993; Gobster and Westphal, 2004) where people can use to reach places of work or study (Toccolini et al., 2004). It was originated from greenbelt and parkway (Turner, 1998).

In agreement with Patricia et.al 2006, this thesis takes the perspective of the environment as a complex web of landscape elements that change and evolve overtime with the landscape composed of patches and corridors that exist within a dominant background, the landscape matrix.

The landscape matrix can be relatively uniform and homogeneous in character or highly heterogeneous and varied over space. Both patches and corridors contrast in appearance with the landscape matrix. The difference between them is that patches are non-linear areas, and corridors are linear arrangements of natural areas or elements that can be considered to be a place or an event.

Figure 1 Model of a greenway network
Source author

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By viewing the landscape in terms of these basic structural elements, a network can be understood as a system of patches and corridors existing within and extracted from the landscape matrix.

Projecting these concepts for planning a greenway network (GN) in an area, the total area, or the total of the case study area, can be defined as the landscape matrix, the focal points of activity or nodes, as patches, and the greenways as corridors. The nodes can be any nonlinear area that demands connectivity that is to be included in the GN. The third element of the system is the corridors or links, which are linear elements which form the main channels of movement thus facilitate flow of energy.

Plate 1 Bridge structure in a corridor
Source: www.corridorsstrategy

Figure 2 patches, nodes, corridors (source; author)

2.2. HISTORY OF GREENWAY CONCEPT

According to Turner the greenway idea is old, rich and goes back at least 3000 years when in the ancient world of Babylon and Egypt, avenues were made for religious processions, military parades, coronations and burials. Avenues were also used in Imperial Rome and in Renaissance towns and gardens and became distinguishing features of baroque cities in Europe. Avenues were used as carriage routes in towns and for dramatic effect in baroque gardens. Early concepts of greenways were ceremonial avenues which developed into boulevards which were often tree-lined (Turner, 1998).

Plate 2 Evolution of greenways
Source: Turner 1998

2.3 DEVELOPMENT OF GREENWAY STRATEGY

The development of greenways was particularly prolific in the USA, as a reaction to the occurrence of runaway urbanisation. (European Greenways Association 2000). The more contemporary history of greenways is focused on developments in North America and Europe. Fredrick Law Olmstead gets to scene as the inventor of greenway planning. He wrote that "A connected system is far more complete and functional than a series of isolated parks." (Grove 1980)

The idea of greenway planning was furthered by landscape and city architects during the late nineteenth century, especially Frederick Olmstead and Charles Eliot in the USA and Ebenezer Howard in the UK. Olmsted's two sons (John and Frederick Jr) and Charles Eliot II were part of a second generation of landscape planners who continued greenway planning (Fabos 1995).

William H. Whyte introduced the greenway concept to a large audience and advanced the term. The term 'greenway' was first used by Whyte in his 1959 monograph *Securing Open Space for Urban America* in a discussion of the work of Edmund Bacon, who prepared a greenway plan for an undeveloped, semi-rural area of northwest Philadelphia (Little 1990).

Plate 3 Corridor strategy
(source; ambertrail.org)

Plate 4 corridor strategy
Source <http://googleimages.com>

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Subsequently Phillip Lewis coined the term 'environmental corridors 'and this was used to plan a major state wide greenway/green space system with a focus on protecting environmentally sensitive areas or river corridors (Fabos 1995).

2.4 BENEFITS OF GREENWAYS

Greenways, because of their key characteristics such as spatial configuration and multifunctionality, they bring to an urban area a wide range of benefits. Based on an exhaustive literature review (Smith, 1993, Turner, 1998, Fabos 1990 and Jim and Chen, 2003, these benefits have been carefully analysed and identified in the figure below. These benefits have been grouped into three parts of sustainability: environmental, economic and social benefits/concerns as follows-:

Figure 3 Illustration of sustainability in greenway networks

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ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

They are a rich source of biodiversity containing different kinds of vegetation –native and non-indigenous plant and animal communities.

Provide wildlife corridors.

SOCIAL BENEFITS

Greenway networks provide spaces for meetings, seminars, campaigns therefore facilitate the coming together of people.

Enhance the facilities for employees awareness of nature and the environment hence could be a means of education.

ECONOMIC BENEFITS

Help inward investment business and also increase real-estate property values.

Provides outdoor recreation and offer tourism opportunities.

ILLUSTRATIONS

Plate 5 (source:photobucket.com)

Plate 6(Source; photobucket.com)

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Enhance environmental quality by creating microclimatic conditions by the availability of water features and vegetation.

Are an alternative transport route especially for the non-motorised transport.

Provide direct employment hence stimulate higher productivity.

Figure 4 (source; author)

Help to restore and protect the natural environments and induce a more efficient way of land utilisation.

Induce healthier lifestyles. They facilitate contact between people and hence help reduce prejudice.

Enable a better appreciation therefore Inducing positive publicity for business thrival.

Plate 7(source; photobucket.com)

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Enhance well-being through contact with nature.
Help to reduce flood hazard and ameliorate Improve the overall appeal of the environment factor.

Have a positive influence on human behaviour. They assist reduce crime rate.

Enable different commercial opportunities.

Figure 5 (source: author)

Are a visual relief, especially in urbanised areas and thus must be kept unpolluted.

Facilitate social equity and therefore a tool for social integration.

Are a cost-effective strategy for traditional parks.

They help boost community sense.

Figure 6 (source; author)

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According to a paper(A greenway network for a more sustainable Auckland, Some of the greenways benefits are reinforced when they are connected in a comprehensive greenway network, linking the main significant areas of natural, ecological, scenic, social, economic, recreational, historical and cultural importance in an area.

The paper argues that a greenway network through its connection and linkage induces a larger spectrum of benefits since this linkage between areas is what makes a greenway network different from more traditional urban parks. Through these benefits, greenways are a sensitive and appropriate response towards greater sustainability therefore becoming a crucial planning tool that

2.5 GREENWAY NETWORKS AND SUSTAINABILITY

Greenways as a tool for both urban and rural sustainability help to enhance can help make progress towards greater urban sustainability and rural sustainability as in this case as well as more other general benefits (Vasconcelos P, Pritchard, & Machado, 1995).

They help enhance;

Figure7 Connection and linkage of spaces (source; author)

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- Quality of life – This entails the improvement of life quality and standard for all the people by meeting all the basic environmental, social and economic aspects of life. Examples for basic environmental elements are water, air, spaces for movement and a desirable habitat for living, recreation and working. Some basic social elements include physical and mental health, access to education and housing, and equity. The basic economic elements are for example reliable employment, incomes that sustain a fair quality of life, and economic opportunities and diversity.
- Land use planning – This is related to the irreversible land use changes and the pace at which land, a finite resource, gets consumed by urban development and urban sprawl.
- Provide good connections –Connections from landscape to landscape, and space to space are important because providing or maintaining connectivity in a landscape supports particular processes and functions of importance that may not otherwise have occurred. In this case therefore, sustainability is argued to be an important aspect of sustainability.
- Sense of place, of identity and of belonging – Areas through their design should support a dynamic cultural life and foster strong identities enhanced by providing a distinctive character to an area. transportation should enhance the quality, liveability and character of communities and support revitalisation.

Figure 8 Model of good connections (source; author)

Figure 9 Greenway networks a tool for social sustainability.

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- Green areas – Important as they aid to provide visual relief, also being used as places for rest or recreation majorly because they help regulate microclimatic conditions by the provision of shade for instance.
- Open spaces – The creation, protection and maintenance of green/open spaces are crucial elements of sustainability, as well as their accessibility by everybody especially the development of networks of (green) open spaces for the protection of natural resources.

Figure 10 Sustainability of greenway networks.(source; author)

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2.6 GREENWAY NETWORKS TO ENHANCE CONTACT EXPERIENCE.

Evaluating the scenery of open spaces requires an examination of all the design components e.g. colour, textures, shapes, vegetation, etc.

2.6.1 BASIC DESIGN ELEMENTS

Landscape elements can be point, line, plane or volume depending on how we see the objects-our distance from them. In order to see how elements interact, an understanding of their individual attributes should be considered and according to Bell 1991 they are as follows-:

Point. These can vary in size, value, regularity or irregularity, and can be used alone or as a unit in a group which forms a line or shape in the image. In the past, points have been described with a specific purpose such as to mark out a territory, to assert ownership or dominion over an area, to act as landmarks, to provide a focus for a grand design, or merely to provide an interest in a featureless landscape.

Figure 11. Model of dot, line, plane and volume on landscape Source; author

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Line. A line is an extension of a point. It is a form with width and length, but no depth. In the landscape lines are seen as streams, edges of vegetation, tree trunks and horizon and rock strata. Field boundaries are examples of manmade lines.

Plane. Formed by extending a one dimensional line into two dimensions. Therefore this is the medium for other treatment such as the application of texture or colour or as a device to an enclose space.

Volume. This is a three dimensional extension of a two dimensional plane and could be geometrical or irregular.

2.6.2 DESIGN VARIABLES

Variables on the landscape how elements are perceived by the users or the observers (Bell, 1993).

These design variables include

- Texture
- Size
- Shape

- Time

Figure 12 Abstract of point, line and volume on the landscape(source ;author)

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- Number
- Direction
- Colour.

On the landscape, spatial attributes are expressed in terms of these variables.

Texture is the feel of and appearance of a surface, how smooth or rough a surface is. So as to experience texture, one has to have intimate space proximity. Different textures are used in different places for different purposes (Bell, 1993), and have different impositions in the minds of their perceivers.

Size is concerned with the dimensions or parts of an element. These variations include large/small, tall/short, wide/narrow, and shallow/deep (Motloch, 1991). On the landscape, sizes determine ratios with comparison to the human scale, which evokes different perceptions and feelings in the users of these places. For example, size becomes of essence when considering the factor of shadows by trees and other landscape features.

Shape/form is the visual appearance of something or someone in the environment. As a perceptual structure; it has got powerful and evocative effects on the way we perceive our surroundings as patterns. It is the primary variable by which a feature is identified.

Figure 13 Size as a design variable

Plate 8 Colour as a design variable (source <http://www.photobucket.com>)

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Time is the fourth dimension (Bell 1993). All real objects change with time and in accordance to the future. Time can be considered to be cyclic (day/night, seasons) or progressive (birth, growth, death).It is related to motion as speed or velocity. In landscape design features in the landscape can be ordered in such a way as to take advantage off or inhibit or slow the effects of time.

Single elements may exist by themselves with apparently little reference to their surroundings. (Motloch 1991).By repetition and multiplication elements will exist in the relationship between scenes and thus the more there is of a landscape element, the more complex the pattern or design.

Bell 1993 regards position as the way or direction in which an object is placed or oriented in the landscape. Lines, planes or objects cause visual forces depending on how they are positioned. The position of forms may be determined by reason other than the aesthetics and in this case based on the reason of enhancing scenery.

Figure 14 Form as a design variable (source; author)

Figure 15 Position as a design variable (source; author)

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This is the property responsible for causing visual sensation (maslow1954).The colour of elements and how they relate to each other in the landscape influence scenery generally. Colours are described by hue, lightness and saturation. True colour is dependent on natural unfiltered light. (Motloch 1991).

Generally, lines such as roads/paths produce a sense of direction by leading a viewer. Similarly, a mass of trees arranged in a specific order may give direction.

2.7 GREENWAY NETWORKS AND SOCIAL COHESION

According to Patricia et. Al 2006, Greenway networks provide good connections – It is important to conserve connections from landscape to landscape, and space to space. It continues to infer that providing or maintaining connectivity in a landscape supports particular processes and functions that may not otherwise occur and if these processes are beneficial, valued by humans and are dependent on connectivity to some extent, then it can be argued that connectivity is an important characteristic of, or a prerequisite for, sustainability.

Figure 16 Direction as a design variable
(source; author)

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From studies evolving around the rise to the early cities, cities grew as a result of migration into the cities by the people either due to order by the kings or because economy was relatively good. When they came together, populations increased and similarly social groups enlarged and hence, more innovations and inventions resulted. In turn, lives become better and more suitable even though at a direct risk due to the negative effects of industrialisation (Johnson & Timothy, 1982).

Thus demographers and sociologists have consistently proved views that human behaviour is greatly affected by the social, political and economic forces and thus these have been used by in many areas and places to define people, their history, social class etc.

In line with the perspective of this thesis, greenway networks will use corridor links to connect the different activity nodes/patches within the landscape matrix. These activity nodes and patches will entail areas that people visit for social, economic and political purposes or shall entail the corridors linking these places and provide spaces for social activities.

This study explores the cohesive aspect that the greenway network strategy with its myriad of benefits that it can be able to achieve. The greenway network will therefore facilitate the flow of people from one place to the other and in the process, the aspect of cohesion will occur within the corridor links, at the nodes and patches

Plate 9 Spaces for cohesion

(source:<http://www.google.com>)

Figure 17 abstract of a greenway network

(source; author)

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2.8 GREENWAYS AND CONTACT EXPERIENCE

According to the contact theory supporting this study, the interaction of people must be pleasurable. And so this infers that the greenway network has to have a spatial design and attractive features that makes the contact between the two groups exciting.

Therefore, this thesis sought to investigate whatever causes conflict between these two groups and whatever brings these two communities together. The findings obtained helped formulate spatial considerations and recommendations for the design project.

The fact that the individual's basic conceptualization determines his/her identity, the thesis sought to investigate whatever gives people in the two counties identity so that the sense of belonging will help form solidarity i.e. strong interpersonal ties and thus be able to adopt themselves to the other ethnic group peacefully.

All these will be achieved when these two ethnic groups will come together with one goal of fostering their social identity, economic livelihoods, political purposes and environmental goals.

Figure 18 Pleasurable contact experience

Figure 10 Exiting designs to enhance pleasurable contact experience(Source;www.googleimages.com)

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2.9 CASE STUDIES

2.9.1 BROOKLYN-QUEENS GREENWAY

Map 7; World map showing New York city (source; <http://upload.wikimedia.org>)

Map 8 Brooklyn and Queens borough in New York Source; (Michael & Benepe, 1988)

The Brooklyn-Queens greenway (BQG) is located in New York City and runs through the two boroughs of Brooklyn and Queens occupied with people of different cultures, amenities and experiences so it becomes a lively way of engaging these two communities.

It is a 40- mile, continuous pedestrian and cyclist route from Coney Island in Brooklyn to Fort Totten, on the long island sound, in Queens—

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linking 13 parks, two botanical gardens, the New York aquarium, the Brooklyn Museum, the New York hall of science, two environmental education centers, four lakes, and numerous ethnic and historic neighborhoods.

The greenway serves to connect patches and corridors including- Coney island, Ocean parkway, Prospect park, Eastern parkway , Highland park/ridge wood reservoir, Forest park, Flushing meadows, Corona park Kissena-Cunningham Corridor, Alley pond park to Fort Totten.

Every of the nine patches have got distinct characteristics but this study brings the two most elaborate patches on board accompanied with few visual illustrations of the other patches and nodes in this greenway network system.

- Ocean Parkway
- Forest Park

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2.9.1.1 OCEAN PARKWAY

It is almost completely residential, however, there are a few businesses, including neighborhood restaurants and grocery stores, on many of the intersecting streets.

Coney Island had become the New York's wild West by the end of the 19th century. The place attracted all kinds of people, from the most wealthy to the low class people. It was an area notorious for its rowdy drinking and gambling halls, prize fights, and rampant dancing activities.

The era's most wealthy and celebrated flocked to Manhattan Beach, where majestic hotels lined the beach. The prosperous middle class summured at Brighton Beach, where the architecture was impressive, but less grand. West Brighton was the buffer zone between the high and low-life. This

was the destination for day-tripping, working class folks who came by steamship, ferry, or trolley to visit beer halls, eat in the restaurants, dance in the dance halls, and try their luck in the penny arcade. This is the section of the beach that became the Coney Island of popular imagination, especially with the advent of pioneering amusement parks: Steeplechase in 1897, Luna Park in 1903, and Dreamland in 1904.

Plate II Brighton Beach fruit stand

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Most people are be tempted to head straight to the Boardwalk, which has many entrances beckoning from Surf Avenue. But Surf Avenue is also well worth exploring in its own right, with many star attractions and a lively pedestrian scene. For bike riders, the Avenue offers an opportunity to stay mounted and rolling when the boardwalk is closed to bike riding.

→ Entrance from Surf avenue to the boardwalk.

→ Surf avenue

→ Entrance from Surf Avenue to the boardwalk.

→ Entrance from surf avenue to the boardwalk

Boardwalk cafés invite people to sit down and watch the parades and skyline.

Plate 12; Views from boardwalk cafes

Heading west on Surf Avenue, Asser Levy/Seaside Park exists. The centerpiece of this park is its amphitheater, whose stage is crowned by a high-tech white tent. The park provides a nice refuge from the hurly-burly of the surrounding streets and the boardwalk, for those just seeking some good old-fashioned green grass and shade.

The zone between West 12th and 13th Streets is the haunt of the outrageous. The happening corner here is West 12th Street and Surf Avenue, where you'll find the Coney Island Sideshow. This modest show house is dedicated to keeping alive the thrilling underbelly of Americana—besides the sideshow, the venue hosts regular burlesque and rock-and-roll shows.

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2.9.1.2 FOREST PARK OF THE Brooklyn- Queensway Greenway

Forest Park is one of the most pristine parks in New York City. Designed by the firm of Frederick Law Olmsted in the 1890's, of the park's 543 acres, 411 are woodland and the rest of the park include a golf course, ballfields, tennis courts, a bandshell, and even a carousel. It was originally purchased by Brooklyn, parcel by parcel, between 1895 and 1898. The land, part of the terminal moraine ridge line, is sloping not useful for farming. It was seen as a recreational resource for outdoors- starved Brooklynites. After the incorporation of Queens into greater New York City in 1898, the land was designated and preserved as part of the Queens park system. At the park, topography and vegetation preserves distinctive glacial features: kettle hole ponds, knobby hilltops (kettles and knobs), and "erratic" boulders. The forest is still largely native red oak and black oak. Many of the trees are over 150 years old. The neighborhoods surrounding the park—Woodhaven, Richmond Hill, Kew Gardens, and Forest Hills— make wonderful side trips.

Metropolitan Avenue
 This avenue contains a number of eatery points for residents and also visitors.

Myrtle Avenue

Map 10; Forest Park

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Forest Park is known as a hiker's park for good reason. Just before you cross Woodhaven Boulevard, you may want to stop and experience the PFC Laurence Strack Pond on foot. Strack Pond is a beautiful kettle pond teeming with life including plants, salamanders, frogs and other wetland species. This pond provides nature lovers with a great spot to see butterflies, red-tailed hawks, and great blue herons. Visitors can enjoy the pond's trail and viewing area while listening to the calls of the Tufted Titmouse, the Baltimore Oriole, and the Kingbird.

Besides all these, the forest park has got boardwalk that is not a sideshow attraction, but a world-class zoological facility. The Aquarium covers 14 acres, is home to 350 species of aquatic wildlife, including penguins, sharks, and seals, and is a terrific place for families and visitors from all over the world coming to visit the place.

Plate 13 Shingle roofed pre-war houses at the edge of the forest. Source (Michael & Benepe, 1988)

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Kissena-Cunningham Corridor.

The Unisphere stands behind a walking tour in Flushing Meadows-Corona Park.

Plate 14 The Unisphere stands behind a walking tour in Flushing Meadows-Corona Park

Plate 16 Fountain of the Fairs

Plate 15 Greenway alongside Meadow Lake

Flushing meadows-Corona Park.

Plate 17 The sonic playground in Underhill Playground

Plate 19 Shaded playgrounds and ball fields are an Underhill Playground feature

Plate 18 Beautiful stone work

IMPORTANT LESSONS FROM THE VISUAL

ILLUSTRATIONS.

- Shape or Form as important attributes for designing spaces in terms of the aesthetic sense thereof. to facilitate cohesion.
- Functionality of spaces is a key aspect in the design of spaces.
- Different textures and colour determine the visual quality and evoke different feelings to the perceiver.

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2.9.2. BAYOUS GREENWAYS

Figure20 showing the pillars of sustainability for Bayou greenways. ((Dr. John Crompton))

Bayous greenway is built upon the main pillars of sustainability: Economic, environmental, physical and mental health of residents.

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Map 12: Bayou greenway <http://www.maps.com>

This greenway system integrates a livable community approach by interconnecting pathways throughout the community with businesses, schools, hospitals, neighborhoods and nature and by utilizing flexible design approaches and context sensitive solutions.

The Bayou Greenway system promotes community cohesion by incorporating unique enhancement measures with continuous public

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involvement and partnership efforts. This greenway system integrates a livable community approach by interconnecting pathways throughout the community with businesses, schools and neighborhoods and by utilizing flexible design approaches and context sensitive solutions. The Bayou Greenway and continue to be an asset to the entire community by accommodating the multi-modal needs of its citizens through the development and coordination of a project that fully embraces environmental excellence.

Figure 24 Spatial attributes of colour, texture, shape and size. source (Dr. John Crompton)

Plate 21 Picture showing Bayou trails being used for biking: Source (Dr. John Crompton)

Plate 22 paths designed for non-motorised transport means

Plate 23 importance of size on visual quality

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2.9.3 CASE STUDY 3 of Berlin of spatial designs that facilitate the lack of cohesiveness

A DIVIDED BERLIN

The Berlin Wall stretched over a hundred miles. It ran not only through the center of Berlin, but also wrapped around West Berlin, entirely cutting West Berlin off from the rest of East Germany.

The Berlin wall was constructed by the German Democratic Republic (GDR, East Germany starting 12th - 13th august 1961 mid-night and it stood till 9th November 1989 when it was primarily destroyed). This was accompanied by the destruction of telephone wires that connected the east and the west.

Living conditions in the East Berlin were repressive. On the other hand West Berlin got support from its occupying powers and had set up a capitalist society that saw enormous economic growth that favoured its citizens to lead better lives.

Map 13 Berlin City

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The wall itself went through four major transformations during its 28-year history before it was pulled down.

The Berlin Wall started out as a barbed-wire fence with concrete posts, but just a few days after the first fence was placed, it was quickly replaced with a sturdier, more permanent structure made out of concrete blocks, topped with barbed wire.

These were replaced by the third version of the Berlin Wall in 1965. This version consisted of a concrete wall, supported by steel girders. The fourth version of the Berlin Wall, constructed from 1975 to 1980, was the most complicated and thorough. It consisted of concrete slabs reaching nearly

2-feet high (3.6 m) and 4-feet wide (1.2 m), plus it had a smooth pipe running across the top to hinder people from scaling the Wall.

Berlin therefore became a city where fragmentation can be clearly read. Not only through the inner-city emptiness, but also because of the many crashes of different realities which can be observed all over the city in this day.

Plate 25-28 showing the four major transformations of the wall during its 28- year old history.

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LESSONS LEARNT

Greenways are dynamic in nature and should be exciting features. Owing to the fact that they connect places of importance i.e recreational, economic, environmental value, etc ,these places should be made to be uniquely different, hence creating unique identity of themselves.

To achieve this, referring to the case studies, values of shape, colour and texture are very important in the design with an objective of bringing people together. In all the case studies across the board, these have brought the issue of unique identities very clearly. Another thing that comes out strongly is the aspect of the functionality of spaces. For example in the Bayou greenways, the multifunctional trail are shaded, providing a serene environment for biking, riding, jogging etc. Similarly, in the Brooklyn-Queen greenways, the features in the playground are shaded. In addition, seats and benches have also been provided for the users of these spaces.

Again, open spaces in the greenway network-nodes and patches act as places cohesion because it is in these places that activities do occur. Further study in the case study of Brooklyn-Queen Forest Park reveals that at the Metropolitan Drive node are places for eating, and recreation- part of the activities that facilitate the coming together of people or public involvement.

Figure 19 Colour, shape and texture as tools of facilitating cohesion.(source; author)

Figure 20 Aactivities that boost cohesion(source ;author)

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In all cases emphasis is put on Non- motorised means of transport e.g. skates, bicycles and foot means. This would make it easier for users to interact at the open spaces.

Further cohesion could be achieved by interconnecting pathways throughout the communities with businesses, schools and neighborhoods and by utilizing flexible design approaches. There are spatial designs that facilitate lack of cohesion. In the case of Berlin, the wall acted as a barrier and thus prevented many people from meeting with others on the other side for 28 years. Relationships were cut because even the telephone wires were cut down. No longer could the East Berliners cross over to meet for operas, plays, soccer games and no longer could the West Berliners move to the East for services are vital tools to enhance cohesion well paying jobs. It is therefore thus evident that transport and communication

Figure 21 Incorporation of other activities to enhance cohesion(source;author)

Figure 22 Open space by other services to enhance cohesion. (Source; author)

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2.10 COHESION IN HISTORY

2.10.1 ANCIENT GREECE 3300- 31 BC

Map Europe in the context of the world

<http://www.worldatlas.com>

Map Greece in the context of the Europe.

<http://www.worldatlas.com>

Map http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/9/9a/Homeric_Greece.svg

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Rational city planning developed during the Late Classical and Hellenistic period throughout Greece. Following the destruction left by the Persians and Peloponnesian Wars, many cities were left decimated and in need of rebuilding. Before rational city planning, cities grew organically and often radiated out from a central point, such as the Acropolis and Agora at the center of Athens.

Hippodamus, a Greek from the city of Miletus on the Ionian coast (what is now the western coast of modern Turkey), was an architect and urban planner who lived between 498 and 408 BCE. He is considered the “father” of urban planning and his name is given to the grid layout of city planning, known as the Hippodamian plan.

The Hippodamian plan, or grid plan, is a city-plan formed by a criss-cross network of streets intersecting at right angles. Hippodamus helped rebuild many Greek cities using this plan. The construction-style was exported to newly settle Greek colonies, and was adopted by Alexander the Great for the cities he founded. It was later used extensively by the Romans for their colonies. The plan not only encompassed the grid pattern for the streets but also designated a standard size for Public spaces of the Greek’s agora and theatres that were located at the center of the city.

Map. A greek city plan

Source: <http://images.greekcity plans>

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Additional space would be cleared for gymnasiums and stadiums and the acropolis. The highest part of the city was always reserved for the city's most important temples.

The Hippodamian plan based on a right-angled grid, ensures that the allocation of public and private spaces are met duly. The center of the city contained the city's most important civic public spaces, including the agora, the bouleuterion, theatres, and temples. Private rooms surround the city's public arenas. Since the Hippodamian plan is based on angles and measurements; it could be laid out uniformly over any kind of terrain. In the city of Priene the plan is laid out over a sloping hillside, and the terrain is terraced to fit into the rational network of houses, streets, and public buildings uniformly over any kind of terrain. In the city of Priene the plan is laid out over a sloping hillside, and the terrain is terraced to fit into the rational network of houses, streets, and public buildings.

Plate 32 Priene, Turkey
<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Priene>

Plate 31 Greek theatre <http://revtravel.com/>

Figure 29 Greek agora and other features
Source: <http://greekcitymaps.com>

Figure 30 Bird view of greek city centers
Source: <http://greekcitymaps.com>

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2.10.2 MESO-AMERICAN URBAN TRADITION 200-900 AD

Map
<http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/en/thumb/5/5b/LocationWHMesoamerica.png/250px->

Map Meso-America source; www.cept.net

Map Meso-America and its different area. source; www.cept.net

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Mesoamerica is a culture area covering central and southern Mexico and northern Central America. It was home to a wide diversity of peoples and cultures, of which the Maya and Aztecs are the best known. The ancient cities and towns of Mesoamerica varied greatly in their size, social composition, economic institutions, administrative role, and religious institutions. Nevertheless, a basic pattern of urban planning was found in most cities and towns.

Because cities were centers for economic, political, and religious activities, many occupational specialists were urbanites. Artisans, merchants, bureaucrats, scribes, priests, and other specialists were found in most Mesoamerican cities, although in varying numbers depending on the size of the city and its functional orientation. Many Mesoamerican cities also contained more than one ethnic group. (Sanders & Barbara, 1968).

Mesoamerican cities varied widely in the degree and nature of urban economic activities and so the time of Spanish conquest (A.D. 1519), marketplaces were prominent features in most Mesoamerican cities, reflecting the importance of commerce at that time.

Map Two Central areas of two Meso-American capitals; Teotihuacan and Tikal.

Source (Sanders & Barbara, 1968)

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Cities were the focal points of Mesoamerican long-distance exchange networks, (Smith, 2002). Urban centers were sacred places, and in addition to conducting ceremonies at the temples and in their compounds, priests often walked in processions in the avenues throughout the city and conducted rituals at various shrines and holy places (such as caves) both within and outside of cities. (Smith, 2002)

2.10.2.1 Planning of the Meso American cities

An ancient and fundamental pattern of urban planning guided the layout of most Mesoamerican cities and towns. The central areas were carefully planned and laid out according to religious and political principles, whereas the surrounding residential zones were unplanned and lacked an overall organizing theme, (Smith E, 1996).

An extensive literature review pertaining planning of the Meso-American cities reveal that the pyramids, palaces, ball courts, and plazas found in the urban core were integrated into a coherent architectural and spatial unit through a combination of common compass orientations and the use of walls and passageways. This arrangement was often dictated by religious ideas, both astronomical and mythological.

Plate 33 Temple and other large buildings in the central area of Tikal. [Photo by Michael E. Smith]

Plate 34 pyramids and plazas

Source; <https://encrypted-bn3.gstatic.com/>

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The central ceremonial plazas of most cities were large open spaces flanked by tall pyramids. When people gathered in the plaza to witness ceremonies or for other business, they could not help but be impressed by the monumental buildings that towered over the plaza.

This pyramid-plaza arrangement, replicated on a smaller scale in other parts of the city, was a component of urban planning whose political message accompanied its overt religious symbolism. Although this pattern of urban planning was widespread in Mesoamerica, not all cities conformed to it. One alternative arrangement was the central Mexican imperial capital pattern.

Teotihuacan, the first large city and the earliest imperial capital in highland central Mexico, shows a high degree of centralized planning over the entire city. All buildings followed a common pattern that was aligned with a central ceremonial avenue, the "Street of the Dead".

According to Turner 1998, these ceremonial avenues are the same that have been developed over time into greenways this day. Streets during this period (200-900AD) were full of traffic mainly because the avenues informed planning and so they were an important element of axis.

Plate 35 Planning of the Meso-American Cities

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2.10.3 BAROQUE PERIOD 1600-1750 AD

Map Europe and Germany in the world context
 Source <http://www.mapsofworld.com/germany/maps/germany-location-map.jpg>

Map of Versailles in France
 Source <http://pics2.city-data.com/city/maps2/cm4511.png>

Map Dresden in Germany Source
<http://www.budalionsclub.com/images/germany-map.jpg>

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In this era, Individual structures and edifices which were perceived as centres of power – palaces, churches, statues and monuments – were used as formal organizational nodes for the surrounding cityscape, ‘constructed and placed with a careful eye to the creation of a vast unity to which such structures alone gave meaning.

Baroque architecture involved the laying out of carefully planned avenues and intersections,(corridor strategy) the use of significant buildings and monuments(patches/activity nodes) as focal points and the organisation of the scheme’s component parts to create vistas and emphasise *points-de-vue*, with axial elements in already existing street patterns frequently being stressed in new urban development. Thus the ‘embellishment of existing towns’ and ‘expansion rather than unfettered creation’ were the characteristics of town and city planning during the baroque era of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries.

During this period, the city of Dresden, a city of independent parts, connected by gardens, streets and squares and co- ordinated into a scheme of vistas and visual effects, developed within an already extant urban matrix.

Map Central Dresden, showing significant buildings and monuments.
Source <http://www.artificialhorizon.org>

Plate36 Zwinger, Dresden (refer map of Dresden)
Source <http://www.artificialhorizon.org>

Plate 37 Hofkirche (refer map of Dresden)
Source; <http://www.artificialhorizon.org>

Plate 38 Frauenkirche (refer map of Dresden)
Source <http://www.artificialhorizon.org>

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The extended and replanned gardens were developed into a large, unified rectangular space, formally laid out with ponds, avenues, hedges, flower borders and pavilions, and opened to the public to become a new urban social space. The symmetrical layout was dominated by the palace, designed by Johann Georg Starcke, which dated from 1678-83.

The garden, the palace, and the arrangement of avenues and other features were related to each other, boulevards and to the overall unified composition. Order and symmetry were made to predominate in the close linkage of house, gardens and early baroque statuary and sculpture. An example to this is the city of Versailles.

Map City of Versailles Source
http://www.lib.utexas.edu/maps/historical/versailles_1866.jpg

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2.10.4 RENAISSANCE PERIOD 1300-1500AD

Map Italy in the world
<http://www.worldatlas.com/atlas/whatsnew/iteu.gif>

Palmanova U.D. Italy By Vincenzo Scamozzi

Figure Palmanova U.D
<http://retravel.com>

Map Italy in Europe <http://www.mapsofworld.com/italy/maps/italy-location-map.jpg>

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2.10.5 TOWN PLANNING CONCEPTS OF THE RENAISSANCE "IDEAL CITY"

by *Vincento Vitruvius*' text 'De Architectura Libri Decem (BC33-22) and Alberti's treatise, 'De re aedificatoria' (1443-45, 1447-52, 1485) are situated at a very important position for understanding the planning methods that the Renaissance architects drew in their Architectural treatises. The perspective views on the town planning expressed in these texts of Vitruvius and Alberti, and the successive ideas drawn in the Ideal City have obvious differences in the output influence. The latter, the successive ideas were visualized as an image of ideal town space.

Plazas

As for the shape of plaza, all three adopt a rectangle shape to the major plaza but each takes over different aspect ratio; 3:2 by Vitruvius, 2:1 by Alberti [Alb_VIII,vi] and also by Scamozzi. Alberti describes about plazas such as that the small plazas should be laid out at intersections of streets [Alb_VIII,vi] but does not refer to such central major plazas as Vitruvius and Scamozzi mention. However the concept of centripetal effect is common to three. As for the town facilities, Vitruvius arranges the major town facilities around the major plaza located in the town centre.

Plate 39 Palmanova U.D Italy Source <http://retravel.com>

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In the architectural treatise by Scamozzi, “*L’idea della Architettura universale*”(Universal Architecture 1615), Scamozzi also assign a major plaza in the town centre and places monarch mansion, cathedral, facility concerning finance, management, justice facility around the plaza. In many of the ideas about the Ideal city, the allocation concept of the sites for town facilities depends, but, in general, a major plaza is located in the town centre to create a strong centricity of whole town to physically create an atmosphere as a town core.

Vitruvius, to increase the functionality of town space. Scamozzi tries to describe a standard scheme of town space using a drawing plan of town. As a whole, Alberti considers more diversity than Vitruvius, and Scamozzi shows normative guidelines with more practicality and application in its town image than Vitruvius and Alberti.

Plate 40 Town space diagram by Scamozzi

2.11 Theoretical framework

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2.12 Analytical framework

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES	TYPE OF DATA	SOURCES OF DATA	DATA COLLECTION TOOLS	DATA ANALYSIS	METHODS OF ANALYSIS
To evaluate the status of green space planning between Bomet and Nyamira counties	Functional /Physical characteristics	Secondary data	Interview schedules Questionnaires	Descriptive analysis	Report analysis
To investigate the presence/absence of rivalry hence interaction levels	Social, economic, political and functional characteristics	Primary data	Interview schedules Questionnaires	Descriptive analysis Diagnostic analysis	Graphs Tables Sketching
To investigate the relationship between the greenpace planning and social cohesion.	Social, economic, political, functional and physical	Primary Secondary data	Interview schedules Questionnaires	Descriptive analysis	Report analysis

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3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Research methodology refers to a way to systematically solve a problem, (Mugenda 1990). The author further adds that it is the actual reasoning of the logic behind the methods being used in the context of a research. It explains why a researcher is using a particular technique and not any other so that the he/she can obtain results that can be used for evaluation by the researcher or others.

This chapter focuses on the design of the experiment to be used to carry out the research project. It outlines the methods to be used to gather data, sampling procedures, sampling design, data organisation, processing, and presentation.

Research ethics also included in the chapter describe the manner or conditions within which the methodology was carried out.

3.2 RESEARCH APPROACH

The main aim of this study was to investigate the potential of greenway network design as a tool to link counties in rivalry as to achieve social cohesion. To acquire the best results, a descriptive study was used because this kind of approach makes maximum provision for protection against bias, maximizing on reliability. (Kothari, 1990)

A descriptive study was used to describe the characteristics of two ethnic communities (Kisii and Kipsigis) in rivalry and the spatial attributes of the area between these communities.

Secondly, a diagnostic study was incorporated to determine the frequency with which something occurs. This will be incorporated so as to measure the frequency within which a community conduct activities that give identity to their community, the frequency within which the two communities meet and the frequency within which intra-ethnic and inter-ethnic activities occur.

So as to obtain adequate and relevant data with high levels of precision, both quantitative and qualitative methods will be used for the purposes of

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data collection, presentation and analysis. Data collection under these methods employed use of appropriate and efficient questionnaires for the sampled out users of spaces together with well-articulated interviews schedules for experts.

3.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design that was used in this study was descriptive design, also descriptive surveys because these provide the true quantitative descriptions of aspects of a universe of people(Simon, 1932)According to Kothari 1990, this form of research design is termed as survey design because it takes consideration all the steps involved in a survey concerning the elements to be suited.

The research was therefore designed as a survey of the predetermined population selected from the users of the environment. The sample frame for this study was 92 and was drawn from the residents of the two counties and will aim to give information on some spatial attributes inherent to the landscape of the region i.e. resources such as rivers, forests,

hills and heritage factors of that area and about interactions amongst the people. This frame was chosen to act best as the representatives of the whole heterogeneous people of these communities.

3.4 RESEARCH SITUS

The setting of the research was in a natural environment, a centre at the Bomet-Nyamira border normally termed as Sotik-Borabu border or Chebilat Centre, a place where people from the two communities meet for different reasons. Canter, 1983 argues that it is the aspect of research situs that helps to know where and how people should move in any research. In this research therefore, the target population was drawn from the two ethnic groups of Bomet and Kipsigis Counties.

Seven centres were chosen as a representative of the two communities, three in Bomet and four in Nyamira County. This disparity occurred as the study covered only the extensive activity areas in the source list found at an approximate linear distance of 3 Km on both sides of the border along the Kisii Highway.

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These centres included

Bomet County :-

- Chepilat
- Moi-Minariet School
- Sotik

Nyamira County :-

- Open space at the boundary.
- Mwongori School
- Damside Hotel
- Onsando.

3.5 DATA SOURCES

According to Simon 1932, any research being carried out where design and the use of the physical environment is at stake should have information such as – physical, economic and functional characteristics of the scope. This research therefore sought for the functionality of the open spaces in

terms of land-use activity and utilization analysis, users views and observation by the researcher.

Therefore the sources of data that were used included:-

Primary data

Secondary data

3.6 RESEARCH METHODS

According to (Mugenda, 1990) the type of research method to be used should match the purpose of the study. The following research methods were therefore used:-

- Interview method.
- Observation method.
- Archival method.

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3.6.1 INTERVIEW METHOD

This was done in the form of organized interview schedules. In this case, a few selected individuals from the population together with a number of resource persons from Planning Department and institutions that are stakeholders in peace establishment were interviewed to obtain relevant information.

3.6.2 OBSERVATION METHOD

This method involves the collection of information by a researcher's own observation without interviewing the respondents. (Kothari, 1990)

Therefore, this method was used in the observation of the utilization of the physical environment of the landscape within the study area.

This method employed:-

- ✓ Non-participatory observation that entailed studying the activities done at the sampled areas.
- ✓ Naturalistic observation that entailed observing the behaviours of people especially at the border zone- Chepilat.

- ✓ Observing the environmental behavior –This was employed in systematically watching of people as they use the environment in form of individuals, pairs of people, small groups or large groups. It also entailed observing the activities that they were doing, and the manner in which the spatial relations were affecting the participants.

3.6.3 ARCHIVAL METHOD

This entailed the use of already documented information for example the maps of both Counties and the study areas from the Survey Departments of both Counties.

3.7 DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUES

Primary data collection was collected using

3.7.1 Questionnaires

These were administered to a population sample that was acquired from the two counties to be a representative of the respective ethnic group. Questions which give the respondents freedom to respond were used

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leading to a variety of responses for the same question (Mugenda and Mugenda, 1999)

The questionnaires were self and research administered where the research method used required assistance for those who could not be able to interpret the questions easily.

3.7.2 Interview Schedules.

These were carried out by the aid of well-articulated interview schedule which were administered to selected individuals from the population, and resource persons.

3.7.3 Photographs and Sketches.

These were used to support the documentation concerning this area and would enable others to fully understand about the area without having being there physically.

3.7.4 GIS Tool

These were used so as to map out zones that were essential in forming the greenway network.

3.7.5 OBSERVATION CHECKLIST

This entailed filling in information concerning the spatial attributes of the areas under study. Some of this information entailed the utilization analysis together with the landscape elements that were in the site. It was most important for comparison purposes between the existing situation on the site and the responses of the respondents.

3.8 SAMPLING DESIGN

As argued by Kothari 2004, sampling design refers to the methods used to obtain sample frame from a given population.

3.8.1. Population and Sample size

The study population in this research included area 3 km approximately on both sides of the border market Chebilat along the Kisii Highway. Through purposive sampling, three areas were selected from Bomet County – Chepilat Market, Moi-Minariet School and Sotik town. While in Nyamira County four areas were selected. These included, Mwongori School, Onsando Neighbourhood, Damside Hotel and an Open Space at the

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boundary. These were chosen so as to fulfill the requirements of efficiency, representation, reliability and flexibility as according to Kothari 1990.

3.7.2. Sampling Unit

To obtain the best information and results the sampling units were drawn from the earlier stated centres based on an assumption that was confirmed during the research, that the people in these area know much about the border zone as they were frequent users of this area or had some other interest in that place.

3.7.3. Sample frame

A sample frame was selected and this involved selecting a source list that entailed -institutional bodies, neighbourhoods, town centres, open spaces and relaxation joints that had users who tended to use the border zones frequently. This source list was employed so as to enhance of collecting comprehensive, correct, reliable and appropriate information that could be generalized to the larger population.

3.7.4. Sampling method

3.7.4.1 Simple random sampling

Since descriptive method was used, random sampling criteria was employed to obtain information that would best take care of the heterogeneous group of users. This was carried out in the issuing of the questionnaires to the respondents at all the seven centers using the following procedure

- ✓ Definition of the target population.
- ✓ Selection of sampling frame for proper coverage.
- ✓ Planning for the procedure of selecting sampling units.
- ✓ Determining the sample size. Since the population is highly heterogeneous on the variables that were being measured, a large number of 92 respondents were used to satisfactorily cover the varying respondents.
- ✓ Selecting the target number based on the sampling units.
- ✓ Conducting fieldwork

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3.7.4.2 Purposive sampling

This was done in the selection of centers from which sampled populations would be drawn and secondly, in the choosing of the aspects to be covered in the source list.

General criteria for selecting the sample frame entailed every third person who passed at the identified point and was conversant with the border zone, Chebilat, and interacted with people from other communities on a daily basis.

3.7.5. Subjects

This study investigated spatial attributes that concerned the spaces that the respondents were in at the time they were being interviewed together with the spaces that they used for socialization purposes.

The study also sought to find out whatever gave communities present identity. Lastly, the study sought to identify activities that facilitated interactions within members of a particular community and with members from other communities.

3.9 PROGRAMME FOR DATA COLLECTION

3.9.1 Pilot study

27/05/2013-11/06/2013	Working out sample tools with supervisor.
11/06/2013	Obtaining letters of permission from the department to conduct data collection
18/06/2013	Interview schedules with Chiefs in Nyamira County and a representative from Border Peace Committee. Issuing of questionnaires at Mogusii and Mwangori centers.
19/06/2013	Issuing of questionnaires at Chepilat and Sotik.(12 in number)
20/06/2013	Obtaining the map of Bomet County from Bomet Information Offices and Bomet Lands offices.
21/06/2013	Obtaining map of Nyamira County from Nyamira County Council offices.

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3.9.2 Actual data collection

13/07/2013	Reviewing of data to be collected and sample tools.
15/07/2013	Issuing of questionnaires to people at Onsando neighbourhood and Damside Hotel in Nyamira County (11 Questionnaires in each case).
16/07/2013	Issuing of questionnaires to people at Mwongori High School in Nyamira County (11 Questionnaires)and similarly at the Open space at Mwongori.
17/07/2013	Delivering questionnaires at Chepilat Town and Moi-Minariet center.
18/07/2013	Delivering questionnaires at Sotik town center.

3.10 DATA PROCESSING

3.10.1 DATA VALUATION

Data validity refers to the degree to which the data collected from the analysis of the data actually reflect the phenomenon under study. A thorough reviewing was performed, and any gaps or shortcomings were resolved. Counterchecking and cross-examining of the respondents account with the situation on the ground was also checked.

3.10.2 DATA EDITING

Data editing was done on two basis-

- Field editing
- Central editing

Field editing: this was done on site to ensure that all the questions were attempted, that all the abbreviations and illegible writings are corrected.

Central editing: This was done away from site, in class and it entailed correcting obvious errors to facilitate easy coding.

3.10.3 DATA CODING

This was done to represent attributes of measured variables, classifying then into classes or groups on the basis of the common characteristics of the responses as obtained from the questionnaires to ensure that an efficient analysis is done.

3.10.4 DATA CLASSIFICATION

This entailed arranging data on the basis of common characteristics.

3.10.5 DATA TABULATION

This involved organising data into more compact forms like by the use of tables, charts and graphs

3.10.6 DATA RELIABILITY

A test is reliable if it measures something consistently. In this study, consistency was ensured by administering a standard questionnaire to all the respondents that were involved. Data from personal observation was crosschecked against the existing secondary data of the study area. The relevance of the collected data will also be established. This was done to facilitate accuracy, completeness and quality of data collected. This entailed

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the establishment of consistency of data obtained from site, if the research was to be carried out repeatedly.

3.10.7 DATA VALIDITY

The validity of data collected from the field involved counter checking the respondents' account through questionnaires and the result from the interviews schedules.

3.11 DATA PRESENTATION

Data obtained was reduced into homogeneous groups so as to establish meaningful relationships. This entailed the systematic organization of the raw data from questionnaires, physical observations and interview schedules in a manner that facilitated easy analysis.

Data obtained from the research methods was presented in the form of:--

- Photographs: These would enable others to have a feeling of the site without necessarily having been there.

- Tables: Data was organised in tables so as to communicate relationships between variables as obtained from the respondents' responses.
- Bar charts and graphs that graphically represent the various variables that were being measured.

3.12 PILOT STUDY AND PRE-TESTS

Pilot study is a mini-version of a full –scale study done in preparation of the full study. refers to trial runs that are carried out in preparation for the major study.(Polit. Et al,2001) or even testing or the trying out of the particular research instruments being used.(Baker, 1994) Therefore this research entailed conducting of a pilot study first and this involved;-

- Developing and testing the adequacy of the research instruments
- Assessing whether the research protocol being used is realistic and workable.
- Establishing whether the sampling frame and the technique are effective.

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- Identifying logistical problems which could occur using the proposed methods
- Collecting preliminary data
- Determining whatever resources are of importance to carry out the collection of data.

3.12.1 PROCEDURES USED FOR CONDUCTING THE PILOT STUDY AND PRE-TESTS

- Questionnaires were administered in exactly the same way that they were to be administered in the actual data collection
- A record of all the ambiguities and difficulties that the respondents were facing were put down.
- A record of the time taken to complete the questionnaire was also recorded to determine whether was reasonable.
- Identification of practical problems of the research procedure.
- Assessment whether every question could give an adequate range of responses

3.12.2 OUTCOMES AS A RESULT OF THE PILOT STUDY DONE

Questionnaires were shortened and revised further so as to save on time.

All the unnecessary difficult and ambiguous questions were discarded.

Provision of adequate range of responses for some of the questions.

Revision of the interview schedules to gather even more appropriate information more relevant to the study.

3.13 RESEARCH ETHICS

The research was carried under four major research ethics principles. The study required the researcher not to put the participants in a situation where they could be at risk or harm as a result of their participation. This involved-

Anonymity. This principle entailed the participant being anonymous throughout the study even to the researcher.

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Confidentiality-Entailed assuring the participants that any identifying information would not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the research study.

Others-;

Informed consent. This entailed giving full information to the prospective research participants about the procedure and risks involved so that they could give their consent to participate.

Voluntary participation. This principle required that people would not be coerced to participate in the research.

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3.14 WORK PLAN and TIME TABLE			WEEKS										
ID	TASK NAME	DURATION (days.)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	Formulating research design and problem	3	█										
2	Literature review	5		█	█	█			█		█		
3	Pilot study	4						█					
4	Processing and analysis of data	4							█	█			
5	Collection of data	4								█	█		
6	Processing and analysis of data	8								█	█		
6	Preparation of the 1 st draft	8									█	█	
7	Revision and enhancement of 1 st draft	14										█	█
8	Final draft	1											█
9	Printing and binding	1											█

3.15 RESEARCH BUDGET

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<u>Item</u>	<u>Specification</u>	<u>Cost(Ksh)</u>	
1	Personal cost	Accomodation and other basic expenses.	10,000
2	Support services	Wage for the researcher's assistant during the pre-tests, pilot study and final data collection.	5,000
3	Field work cost	Transport and other expenses	15000
4	Overheads	Stationery materials, photocopying, printing, and binding services.	7000
5	Books/journal cost	Books, journals and any relevant material	2,000
6	Equipment/facilities	Equipment	2,700
7	miscellaneous		3,100
Total cost			44,900(Ksh)

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4.0 STUDY AREA

This Chapter focuses on the history and development of the area, the physiographic and natural conditions of the area and the proposed frameworks, both legal and institutional that governs the area of study.

4.1 PHYSIOGRAPHIC AND NATURAL CONDITIONS

Sotik covers 537.0 Km² and arable land constitutes 82 percent of the land with irrigated land 57 % taking up 14 percent, forest land 4 percent. There is no arid and semi-arid land (Muriu & Owino,2009). Sotik is mainly inhabited by the Kipsigis who are a Kalenjin subtribe.'

On the other hand, Borabu strides both Nyamira and Kisii district and is inhabited by the Abagusii people. The area is mostly hilly and is dissected by rivers flowing west into Lake Victoria. The area lies on a highland equatorial climate, and as such receives rain almost throughout the year, although there are two rainy seasons (March to May and October to November).

Plate 1 Chebilat Border centre

Plate 2 Tea plantations source author

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Average rainfall is over 1500mm and is quite reliable, helping to support, tea, and subsistence crops (maize, beans, millet, potatoes). Temperatures can range from 10°C to 30°C. Due to the high population density, almost all land in this area is put to maximum agricultural use.

The most outstanding vegetation in the area are;

TREE/SHRUB	SCIENTIFIC NAME	FAMILY NAME
BLUE GUM TREE	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>	Myrtaceae
SILKY OAK TREE	<i>Grivellia robusta</i>	Proteaceae
CYPRESS TREE	<i>Cupressus spp.</i>	Cupressaceae
BLACK WATTLE	<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>	Fabaceae
TEA	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Theaceae
BANANAS	<i>Musa acuminata</i>	Musaceae
NAPIER GRASS	<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i>	Poaceae
Maize	<i>Zea mays</i>	Poaceae

The Sotik

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transvaalensis (royal blue grass), and eragrostis atrovireus.

4.2 HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE AREA

4.2.1. History of Ethnic intolerance between the Kisii and the Kipsigis.

Even though large scale ethnic violence seems to have started in 1991 in the Larger Rift Valley Province (Kimenyi & Ndung'u, 2005.), ethnic violence in this region has been going on since the 1800's albeit on a limited scale (Morgan, 1963). According to Morgan (1963), the area under contestation was the only fully documented instance of settlement schemes which were deliberately encouraged to separate two warring tribes.

4.2.2. 'Planned for' fragmentation

Apparently as early as the 1960's the fighting between the Abagusii and the Kipsigis had gotten so bad that the colonial government set out to alienate land and create a buffer zone between the tribes. According to Morgan (1963), the pastoral Kipsigis to the East were in a state of semi-permanent hostilities with the cultivating Kisii to the west. Government officers

Plate 7 Fragmentation source author

Plate 8 Fragmentation source author

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inspected the area in 1906 and recommended that this 58 block of land was suitable for farming by Europeans and should be settled as a buffer zone. According to the same author the land was pastoral and known to belong to the Kipsigis, but as hoped that the loss of this land would force the tribe to become more agricultural, and thus settled, on the ample land remaining to them.

4.2.3 Continued conflicts

The Kipsigis argue that the land comprising Borabu district is their ancestral land (Mars Group, 2008). They claim that they lost it when the Europeans forcibly acquired it during the colonial times to establish White highlands. At independence, the Kisii, Kipsigis, and the Maasai were given the opportunity to buy the land at the White highlands partly forming the present border area between the Kipsigis and the Kisii. They bought the land from the departing Colonial Settlers through an arrangement facilitated by the Settlement Fund Trustee. The Kisii's were the greatest beneficiaries of the settlement Schemes among the three communities, because of their higher population density. The Kisii continued to buy land directly in Bomet and Narok, which explains their significant presence in those areas.

Plate 9 Lands majorly aricultural

Plate 10 Border neighbourhoods

4.2.4 Existing rivalry

The rivalry between the two communities predates the colonial era, and this rivalry gets passed down through folklore from generation to generation by both the Kisii and the Kipsigis, each side exalting their own valiant exploits against the other. Since independence the Kipsigis have launched several ambitious campaigns, to recover what they perceive as their ancestral land (Ndegwa, 1997). They launched major attacks against the Kisii in 1964, 1969, 1992, 1997, 2002, and 2007. Their goal is to push the Kisii deep to a place called Meta Maywa.

4.3 LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

4.3.1 The Government Lands Act, Chapter 280 of the Laws of Kenya

This act governs government lands that are vested in the President who make grants or dispositions of any estates, interests or rights in or over unalienated government land.

Unalienated government land in this case is land that which is not presently leased to any person and in respect of which the Commissioner of Lands has not issued a letter of allotment. Some of these powers have been delegated and are exercised by the Commissioner of Lands.

4.3.2 The Forest Act (Act Number 7 of 2005)

Parts of the project area consist of manmade forests. This act elaborates on law which was enacted by Parliament in 2005 to provide

for the establishment, development and sustainable management including the conservation and rational utilization of forest resources for the socio-economic development of the country. forests and woodlands to be managed on a sustainable basis for the purposes of conservation of water, soil and biodiversity, riverline and shoreline protection, sustainable production of wood and non-wood products. Participation by the Communities as provided for under Section 46 of the Act should be Encouraged so that these forests can be conserved.

4.3.3 Physical Planning Act, 1999

This Act makes provision for development control. The Local Authorities are empowered under section 29 of the Act to reserve and maintain all land planned for open spaces, parks, urban forests and green belts. The same section, therefore allows for the

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prohibition or control of the use and development of land and buildings in the interest of proper and orderly development of an area. In the development of any land, approval must be obtained from the relevant local authority. Section 30 states that any person who carries out development without development permission will be required to restore the land to its original condition. It also states that no other licensing authority shall grant a license for commercial or industrial use or occupation of any building without a development permission granted by the respective local authority.

4.3.4 Vision 2030

This development strategy seeks to establish Kenya as a middle income country by 2030. Based on the three pillars of economic, social and political development, this thesis seeks to set a platform that will promote these three pillars directly or indirectly. The greenway network too, with its myriad of opportunities that it can offer on implementation, economic and social functions.

4.4 INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

Development is spearheaded and steered by institutional systems as part of their management function and this thesis proposes to strengthen the institutional capacity for proper collaboration and effective service delivery.

Measures should be put to build local capacities within local institutions, involve the local stakeholders and the public in decision making, and build partnership in local development institutions.

Public awareness will help inform the public on appropriate decision making process, diversification of financial resources and improving collection and management of revenue is expected to provide the much needed resources for the proposed greenway network implementation.

The figures below present the existing legal framework governing counties and the proposed institutional framework that would be essential to oversee the development of the greenway network that connects the two counties.

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4.4.1 EXISTING COUNTY GOVERNANCE

(Figure 3 County governance as it exists source <http://www.google.com>)

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4.4.2 Proposed institutional set Up

Figure 4 Proposed institutional framework (source ;author)

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4.4.2.1 Role of stakeholders

STAKEHOLDER	ROLE
The public	To participate in the decision making process by giving ideas views and opinions
Private sector	To provide relevant services and incentives to be invested in the development of a greenway network system
NGOs,CBOs, and Civil Society groups	To monitor and finance the development process
The Government	To develop and to give policy guidelines for the the establishment and development of a greenway network system. To provide a conducive political environment for implementation. To facilitate the development of all the supporting services e.g service and communication facilities, and infrastructural facilities important towards the realization of the greenway network.

Figure 5Table showing the role of stake holders

Source; author

CHAPTER 5.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The chapter focusses on data analysis and making meaningful relationships.

5.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Data collection in the course of this research entailed preliminary data collection during the pilot study and the actual data collection. Therefore information in this chapter is organised into two major chapters of the pilot study and the actual data collection. Information in the data collection is guided by the research objectives.

Data collection was basically done through the use of questionnaires and interview schedules during the actual data collection

5.2 PILOT STUDY

In Nyamira this entailed conducting discussions with three elders, an assistant chief and two community representatives while in Bomet this entailed discussions with two retired civil servants, a businessman, and an evangelist. The businessman having lived in the area for over 70 years was reknown for his experience concerning the history of the area from the colonial period. Together with the retired civil servants, these people were very helpful in terms of giving information.

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5.2.1 Ammendments as a result of the Pilot Study

There was addition of more centers so as to cater for the heterogenous group. In Bomet Moi-Minariet was added while in Nyamira, Mogusii was dropped down and three other chosen including- Open space area at the boundary, Onsando neighbourhood together with Damside Hotel were added. Mogusii was dropped down so that all the source lists could be met in both counties. In this case, Mogusii has more similar characteristics with Mwongori since both are neighbourhoods.

Revision of the questionnaires to make them short and precise, removing some questions that could not give a range of responses from the respondents..

5.2.2 Data Collection during the Pilot Study

Most respondents stated that the visual quality of the greenspace planning between Bomet and Nyamira counties was good. They attributed this to the availability of the many natural and semi-natural greenspaces that had vast vegetation covers including man-made forests, rich biodiversity, economic values attributed to these green spaces and scenic views on all the sides to the steep ravines of the Kisii and Kalenjin Highlands and their respective beautiful tea scapes.

Plate 1 Nyamira highlands

(source;<http://www.retravel.com>)

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

5.2.2.1 Safety and Security

Safety and security was a great issue of concern by most of the residents. Most of the respondents best described security to be poor. A brief discussion with a resident of Chebilat verified the response from many of the respondents. Insecurity instances, from the discussion with the resident, mostly occurred at night on normal days but proved rampant during the periods of clashes (1992 and 2007 Post-election Violence) where very many people lost their lives and property together with women raping and other murder cases for travellers using the Sotik – Kisii Highway passing through this area. Something was very clear as a result of the focussed group discussions in both counties. One, just at the border line, a police post exists. Within the town centre, the General Service Unit together with The Administration Police are located. All these work force coordinate patrols along the border to ensure that there is law and order. Two, peace resultative committees have been formed i.e. Border committee formed by representatives from both communities and Peace Committee formed by elders in each of the respective ethnic communities.

Figure 1

Figure 2

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

Clearly many efforts have been put to ensure security but still security rates by most respondents rates poor.

5.2.2.2 Connectivity

Connectivity in the greenspace planning ranged good to fair. This connectivity has contributed to contact and cohesion by the two communities though not to the sufficient levels.

5.2.2.3 Street widths

Most respondents find the street widths poor. From the focussed group discussion, it was evident that the narrow streets present at the Sotik - Borabu border have been the result of many of the insecurity poses in the area especially at night and during the rainy seasons. This was also attributed to the conflict of movement high traffic that was using the area.

Figure 3

Figure 4

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

5.2.2.4 Traffic volumes

Traffic volumes around this area range between good and fair. Traffic in this area is composed of people moving to and fro the center for market purposes, people going to work, people going to church and hospital, primary school children going to and fro school etc

5.2.2.5 Vegetation Canopy

According to the chart the vegetation canopy by most respondents is extremely good. The common grasses found in this area are Loudetia kagerensis, Brachiaria soluta and Eragrostis atrovireus. The most outstanding vegetation in the area are Eucalyptus spp, Grivellia robusta (silky oak), Cupressus spp (cypress), Acacia mearnsii(), Camellia sinensis (tea), Musa acuminata (banana), Pennisetum purpureum (napier grass) and Zea mays (maize).

Figure 5

Figure 6

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

5.2.2.6 Sustainability

The good sustainability levels in the greenspace planning between Bomet and Nyamira Counties(see figure 7), with respect to the group discussions with the elders and assistant chief, were attributed to the availability of green environments, good to fair connections between places, a fairly good transport system, a sense of identity and belonging by the two communities that enhance/boost the quality of life.

Figure 7

Figure 8

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

5.2.2.7 Functionality of spaces

Most respondents find different typologies to be economical. This was because

- ✓ Different typologies could be used for different activities.
- ✓ Amenity spaces in the town centres are used for economical reasons e.g. for small roadside businesses.
- ✓ Public typologies are able to host large groups.
- ✓ Everyone was entitled to the public spaces.

5.2.2.8 Intra-ethnic interactions

People like interacting amongst their ethnic group. This is because they have developed trust amongst themselves. From the charts, we even see that even intra-ethnic cohesion is extremely good.

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

5.2.2.9 Interethnic interactions

People avoid interacting with members of other communities. This is because of the rivalry that exists between them. Suspicion between communities since post-election violence period has been evident but has been reducing over time.

Figure 12

Figure 13

5.3 ACTUAL DATA COLLECTION

5.3.1 BOMET COUNTY

5.3.1.1 BEAUTY

Respondents in Sotik have varied opinions concerning the beauty associated with the town. 20% rate beauty to be extremely good, 45% rate this aspect to be good and a discussion with these respondents showed that it was majorly due to the economic values attached to it. In spite of this, 25% rate it to be fair and the minority 5% rate it to be poor while the rest 5% are not sure. These respondents attributed this to the lack of maintenance for the open spaces .

In Moi-Minaret most respondents find beauty of the open spaces to be either extremely good or good i.e. 29% and 53%. This is due to the beautiful foliage, well maintained gardens, and greenery. A small portion 18% of the respondents were not sure.

In Chebilat, (see next page) majority of responses ranged between good and fair i.e. 54% and 31% respectively as a result of the good distant views of the teascapes in the Nyamira

SOTIK

Figure 14

MOI-MINARIET

Figure 15

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

highlands.7.5% rated beauty to be extremely good and the rest 7.5% rated it to be poor majorly due to drainage difficulties, unmaintained vegetation etc.

5.3.1.2 SHAPE

In Sotik, majority of the respondents,35% rated Sotik Town as a town with a good shape. This was attributed to the well-articulated streets with proper drainage systems,and the well maintained buildings e.t.c In Moi-Minariet, 41% rated open spaces to be extremely good, and 12% rate shape to be extremely good. Clearly the school has good structures that are well built and maintained, being surrounded by rich vegetation all around. 29% find the shape to be fair at Chebilat Town, 63% rate Chebilat as having good shape associating them to the availability of green spaces, forests and the ability to appreciate the distant highlands of Nyamira highlands.

5.3.1.3 COLOUR

In Sotik majority of respondents 40% rate colour to be good. This is as a result of the beautiful foliage planted in the area. In Moi-Minariet, 59% rate colour to be extremely good. The area has got well maintained beautiful gardens with different kinds of vegetation that have different colours, and the colour of the structures also blend with that of the landscape. At Chepilat, 31% rate colour to be extremely good and 38% rate this spatial attribute to be.

CHEBILAT

Figure16

SOTIK

Figure 17

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

good. This is majorly because of the scenic views of the distant Nyamira highlands attributed to this place

5.3.1.4 FUNCTIONALITY.

In Sotik 20% rate functionality to be extremely good while 55% rate the same as good. This is generally due to the fact that the town is able to meet at least all the needs of the people(recreational, economical, social etc.).In Moi-Minariet 24% rate functionality to be extremely good and 41% rate this to be good. In times of water shortages for instance these respondents claimed to fetch water form a nearby river, their religious requirements also were duly met at their place and educational needs fulfilled at the same point. At Chepilat too, majority 38% rate functionality as extremely good while 31% rate as good.

MOI-MINARIET

Figure 15

CHEBILAT

Figure 16

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

5.3.1.5 INTERACTION WITH COMMUNITY MEMBERS

In all the samples drawn, it is clear that interaction with community members takes lead generally across the board. People prefer interacting among their own ethnic group. i.e. 50% and 40% in Sotik rate this aspect as extremely good and good 47 % and 30%,also in Moi - Minariet and 38% and 23% in Chebilat too respectively.

5.3.1.6 INTERACTION WITH OTHER COMMUNITY MEMBERS

In Sotik, 40% rate this to be extremely good and 30% to be good.in Moi- Minariet, 53% rate this to be extremely good and 40% to be good. Trend in these two centres are almost similar in that most inhabitants come from different regions who are meeting for educational purpose majorly. In Chebilat however, this trend changes significantly to depict 31% of the respondents rating interaction with members of other communities to be good and 38% rating the same to be fair. This center, located just at the border experience a mixture of ethnic groups majorly the Kipsigis from Bomet who meet at the basis of trading and other economic activities.

5.3.1.7 OPINION OF INDIVIDUALS CONCERNING INTERACTION WITH COMMUNITY MEMBERS

In Sotik, 15% rate this as extremely good and 65% rate this as good. In Moi-Minariet, 41% rate this as extremely good and another 41% rate this as good. Due to issues earlier raised

SOTIK

Figure 17 b

MOI-MINARIET

Figure 15b

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

concerning this two centres the users have learnt to co-exist therefore they perceive this to be something extremely good or good. This is however not the case as in Chepilat. 31% perceive this to be good, 38% perceive this to be fair while 16% are not sure. A discussion with a resident shows that they fear intra-tribal interactions as this could result to various forms of suspicions.

figure 16 b

Plate 5 SOTIK CENTER by author

Plate2 CHEBILAT CENTER Source; author

Plate 3 & 4 MOI-MINARIET CENTER by author

CHEBILAT

OREMO MONYENYE D

AB242-0201/2008

ABL 2501

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5.3.2 NYAMIRA COUNTY

5.3.2.1 BEAUTY

Majority of the respondents perceive this as extremely good or good. For instance in Mwangori School, 48% and other 43% rate beauty to be extremely good and good respectively. At the open space at the border in Mwangori, majority rate beauty to be 40% extremely good while another 40% rate this to good. At Onsando neighbourhood, 55% find beauty to be extremely good and another 45% find the same to be good. This is because the neighbourhood has a serene environment that residents really treasure. Finally, beauty at Damside is rated by 20% to be extremely good and 70% to be good. This place has got well maintained greenery, seating areas and a large water feature.

5.3.2.2 SHAPE

At Mwangori Secondary School, majority of the respondents rate this aspect to be extremely good is 50%. At the open space at the border in Mwangori, 40% rate this as good, a 30% rate as fair and the rest 30% are not sure. This is attributed to lack of maintenance of this area. In addition to this, this open space has poses of insecurity issues. At Damside, 20% find the shape to be extremely good, and another 50% rate the same as good. Forms in this place are generally good, the aesthetic bit of forms e.g. gazebos, open space are generally good.

MWONGORI HIGH SCHOOL

Figure 18

OPEN SPACE AT THE BORDER IN MWONGORI

Figure 19

Onsando, 18% rate shape to be extremely good and a 73% rate this place to be good. Majorly

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

linear along the Kisii highway residents are able to walk with ease to the main road and other places for other activities.

5.3.2.3 COLOUR

Majority of respondents in Nyamira County rate colour to be either extremely good or good. Respondents at Mwongori rate this at 36% and 43%., At the open space at the border in Mwongori,respondents rate colour at 10% and 60% in Damside 30% and 40% and in Onsando 27% and 45% where the first percentage represents extremely good and the other represent good.

5.3.2.4 FUNCTIONALITY

In all the centres, majority of the respondents rate the functionality of the centres to be extremely good and good. The lesser minority are not sure about the functionality or according to them the functionality of these places to be fair or poor. Most of the lesser minority were respondents who were either visitors or had not resided for long in the area.

DAMSID HOTEL

OREMO MONYENYE D

Figure 20

ONSANDO NEIGHBOURHOOD

Figure 21

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

5.3.2.5 INTERACTING WITH MEMBERS OF THE COMMUNITY

Rating by respondents depict that people seem to like with members of their ethnic groups. At Mwangori Secondary, interaction levels of members of the same group rates 36% as extremely good and 43% as good. Located within Nyamira County, approximately 4km from the border, the school has 92% of the students from the Kisii community. Interactions were seemingly good as they shared common values among themselves. At the Open space at the border in Mwangori, interaction rates 30% extremely good and 50% as good. At Damside, interaction rates 80% good and at Onsando the interaction levels are at 27% extremely good and 45% good levels of interaction.

MWONGORI HIGH SCHOOL

Figure 18b

OPEN SPACE AT THE BOUNDARY

Figure 19b

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

5.3.2.6 INTERACTING WITH MEMBERS OF OTHER COMMUNITIES

At Mwangori 21% rate this aspect to be extremely good, 29% rate this as good another 14% rate this as fair, 14% are not sure, and the other 22% rate this as poor. This is a school in which most students are from the Kisii community and a few minorities are from other communities.

At the open space at the boundary in Mwangori, 30% of the respondents rate this form of interaction to be extremely good, 30% to be good, 30% are not sure and 10% rate this to be fair. These interactions occur daily or weekly at the border market, at churches, or in the streets.

At Damside, interaction with members of other communities rates 30% as extremely good while 40% of the respondents find it to be good. Being a hotel, besides the Kisii highway, this place experiences lot of visitors who come here for recreation purposes, meetings and lodging.

At Onsando, also situated along the highway, experiences a rate of 45% interaction levels as good. 18% are not sure while 27% rate interactions to be fair. A discussion with a resident show that this neighbours from Kipsigis community would steal stock from them.

MWONGORI HIGH SCHOOL

Figure 18b

OPEN SPACE AT THE BOUNDARY IN MWONGORI

Figure 19b

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PERCEPTION OF INTERACTING WITH OWN COMMUNITY MEMBERS

At all centers, it is clear that majority perceive this as either extremely good or bad. Based on the reaction of most respondents, they trust community members and cooperate with them to a greater extent than with members of other communities. In accordance to the graphs, we see that, we see that respondents at Mwongori High School rate interactions with community members to be 22% extremely good ,and 57% good, at Mwongori 20% and 60%, at Damside 30% and 50% and Onsando 55% and 36% respectively.

5.3.2.7 PERCEPTION OF INTERACTING WITH OWN COMMUNITY MEMBERS

At Mwongori High School, 21% perceive this to be extremely good, 36% perceive this as good, 29% perceive this as fair and 14% perceive this as poor. At the open space in Mwongori at the border, 60% of the respondents perceive this as good. this is so as to enhance peace between the two communities. At Damside, respondents perceive interactions 30% as extremely good and 60% as good. A discussion with the management officer revealed that the hotel encourages visitors from all parts of the country and world in the business of marketing the hotel. At Onsando, 9% perceive this as extremely good while 64 % perceive this as good

DAMSIDE

Figure 20 b

ONSANDO

Figure 21 b

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From the data that was collected, the research found that Kiswahili, English, Kisii and Kalenjin languages dominate a lot. At Chepilat, the four languages are spoken, at Moi- Minariet school, people speak English and Kiswahili, at Sotik the four languages are spoken. In Nyamira county, at Onsando together with Damside Hotel, Kiswahili and English languages are extensively used by the majority. At Mwongori and at the open space area at the boundary however, majority use kisii and Kiswahili.

Not all the respondents have ever witnessed conflicts and those who ever did, it was as a result of the post-election violence and other general conflicts due to crime and village problems.

Plat 6 Onsando Neighbourhood by author

Plate 10 Open space at the boundary by author

Plate 7 Onsando Neighbourhood by author

Plate 9 Mwongori center by author

Plate 8 Damside Hotel by author

5.3.3 IDENTITY INFORMATION

The study sought to identify activities that give identity to the specific communities and they entailed the following:-

5.3.3.1 Kipsigis community from Bomet County

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	PLACE
Sports	Everyday	Schools, Fields
Birth Ceremonies	Undefined	Village setting
Initiation Ceremonies	Annually	Forests, Village setting.
Marriage Ceremonies	Undefined	Village setting ,Churches
Cultural ceremonies	Undefined	Homes, Villages
Tea Farming	Throughout	Farmlands
Dairy Farming	Throughout	Ranches Farmlands
Business	Daily	Market Centres

Table 1, activities that give the Kipsigis identity Source; author

5.3.3.2 Kisii Community from Nyamira County

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	PLACE
Birth Ceremonies	Undefined	Homes/Villages,
Initiation ceremonies	Annually	Village setting
Marriage ceremonies	Undefined	Village setting, Open fields
Tea Farming	Throughout	Settlement Schemes
Religion	Weekly	Churches
Business	Daily	Village, Market Centres
Welfare Organisations	Monthly	Village, Churches
Witchcraft	Undefined	Undefined
Festivals	Monthly	School playgrounds, Open fields

Table 2, activities that give the Kisii community identity. Source; author

5.3.4 SOCIAL NETWORKS

Activities that bring the two communities together include;-

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	PLACE
Intermarriages	Undefined	Churches, Villages
Self-help group	Monthly	Social hall
Merry-go-round	Undefined	Homes, Village setting
Cattle raiding	Undefined	Border Homes and Villages
Barazas	Undefined	Battle Ground at the border
Peace meetings	Undefined	Battle Ground at the border
Religious meetings	Daily, Weekly	Churches, Homes
Trade	Daily	Market centres
Civic meetings	Undefined	Open fields, Chief's camps
Meetings on public holidays	Undefined	Open fields, Chief's camps
Fundraising Activities	Undefined	Homes, Villages
Institutions	Throughout	Schools, Town Centres.

Table 3, activities that give the bring the Kipsigis and Kisii communities identity
Source; author

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From the pilot study, interviews carried out some of the programmes and projects that would promote cohesion between people of the two communities would include agricultural projects, formation of youth groups, counselling programmes, religious functions, trade and seminars.

5.3.5 EXPERT AND PROFESSIONALS OPINIONS

These are Kenyans above 30 years working in various Government institutions and private institutions. These include a planner from Kisii county, a Planner from Bomet Planning Department and a Surveyor from Bomet.

Planning and Integration Information

General findings from an interview with the experts revealed that:

- There should be an integrated network of streets to enhance interactions. The highway should be clearly defined and vegetation maintained low at bends to enhance visual acuity. To enhance interactions along the highways, nodes could be made at areas with scenic importances attached to them .e.g. at the river areas.

Figure 22 Strategic placements of objects for aesthetics (source; author)

Figure 23 Open spaces are a tool for cohesion (source; author)

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They felt that the establishment of a greenway network that links counties to enhance cohesion would entail a collective responsibility between stakeholder and the Government. Lack of enough technical knowhow and professionalism on the part of local authorities has resulted to the lack of the component of integration in the open spaces. Thus, the local authorities have not endeavoured to develop space for social interactions in these areas. The local authorities should put in efforts to improve the conditions of spaces and also facilitate the development of an integrated network of streets, landscape elements, adding aesthetics to spaces in efforts to improve the visual quality of the spaces.

Components of integration should be incorporated in the planning of open spaces.

Others

Insecurity instances are generally low but are considerably high at the border zones.

Rivalry between the Kisii and Kipsigis Community is majorly on the basis of stock theft.

Existing landscape elements in the open spaces do not have clear symbolic meanings; there is no adequate background information to explain their historical development.

In both communities, soft landscapes have been used for medicinal purpose in history.

Figure24 components of integration source; author

Figure 25 improving visual acuity by proper lighting

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5.3.6 OBSERVATION CHECKLIST

Ownership :Includes both public and private spaces, under the jurisdictions of the county governance of the two counties of Bomet and Kipsigis.

Spatial Observations of the areas under study.

Number	Place	Observations(Activities)	Landscape Element
1	Chebilat	Activities-Social activities, religious, commercial, Services-Power and electricity offices, banking, transport, industrial (KCC), Educational, Petrol Stations.	Road Signs, Left over spaces, Forests, Distant views.
2	Moi-Minariet	Educational, Residential, Walk through, Transport.	Has enough spaces, Trees along the highway that create aesthetics, Bus station.
3	Sotik	Activities-Recreational, Social, Transport, Commercial activities, Civic offices Services- Banking(Equity, KCB) Educational, Petrol Station.	Bill boards, Left over spaces, Distant scenery and views.
4	Mwongori School	Educational	Bill board, vegetation used for screening, use of mixed surface materials-concrete, murrum etc.
5	Boundary Open Space	Cattle grazing, Walking through, Social activities	Neighbourhood, Forest

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6	Damside Hotel	Bird watching, Fishing, Commercial Activities, Walk through	Large Water Feature, Gazebos, Parking Lots, Bus stop, Bill boards.
7	Onsando	Neighbourhood, Educational, Agricultural, Walk through, Bird watching,	Bill board, pedestrian circulation, Forest, Trees along highway for aesthetics, Agricultural activities

Table 4 Observation checklist (source; author)

CHAPTER 6

Deals with implications (Theoretical, Methodological and Practical), and conclusions and recommendations(Policy and Design).

6.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 INTRODUCTION.

This chapter focuses on the implications of the research theoretically, methodologically and also practically in case of implementation. Besides this, the chapter entail general conclusions as a result extensive/broad literature review together with research that thoroughly was done. All these have informed the policy recommendations and spatial guidelines at the end of the chapter.

6.2 THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS.

It is of importance to note that open spaces in the greenway network systems are key in promoting cohesion among people, as from the findings and the literature review.

Fraser 2005 identifies social integration as a framework for representation, redistribution and recognition whereby representation means to stand in for everyone being represented in all endeavours to promote integration, redistribution means the equal allocation of resources, tools, components that promote integration to all in equal measure and recognition to mean the identification of the individual's hence community's identities, common values and social needs.

Representation and recognition add significantly into the inter-personal ties theory that makes an individual hence a community be able to relate itself to a larger society hence fostering integration

Figure 1. Open spaces are key in enhancing cohesion.

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and therefore cohesion.it is also worthwhile to note that sustainable integration runs parallel with cohesion.

Redistribution and contact theory on the other hand build into each other because redistribution oversees equal distribution of all the components of integration to all in equal measure.

Contact theory only occurs in such a case. This theory stipulates that there has to be equality in the status of the people hence community of the people who are interacting having a common objective.

Where representation and redistribution are carried out effectively, recognition results therefore, social integration hence social cohesion. This can be enhanced using greenway networks between through fair representation, equal representation and recognition.

6.3 PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The implementation of the greenway network for cohesion purposes will entail collaborative partnerships between

- The general involvement of public from both counties, for the purposes of their commitment and support, the stakeholders for decision making and funding and finally the trained professionals and leaders to bring it to realization.
- The administrative systems of the two counties.

6.3.1 Involvement of Public, Stakeholders and Professionals

The role of communities is a significant factor in the development of greenways. According to Bryant (2006), greenways are one of the most successful community-level conservation strategies of the past two decades.

Public involvement is generally beneficial to the implementation of greenways.

Greenway projects that encompass public involvement have a greater possibility of being implemented than those that do not (Ryder 1995). Due to the fact that many greenway projects are instigated and implemented at the local level, the public has become a key stakeholder in the greenway collaboration process.

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The general public have their own version of local knowledge or expertise that can help ensure that policies proposed in plans reflect local conditions and values (Kaplan et al 1998; Burby 2003). By involving these stakeholders, professionals will also assist the public's understanding of planning issues.

6.3.2 Multiple Jurisdictions

The very nature of greenways following natural landscape features in this case open spaces and being linear in their length means that implementation of a greenway project usually means that they cross multiple jurisdictional boundaries (Hoover and Shannon 1995). Ryan et al (2004, 173) suggest that implementing greenways, especially across multi-jurisdictional boundaries, can be challenging if not impossible.

Therefore in any given greenway project, the multitude of stakeholders involved, may include more than one Local Government, the state government and its agencies, the federal government, as well as local community groups, local residents and landowners. In this case, this will entail The Government of Kenya, the respective Ministries, Bomet and Nyamira County Governments, local Community Based Organisations, Non-

Governmental Organisations, local community groups, local residents and land owners.

6.3.3 Physical Barriers, Public Acquisition of Land and Private Property Rights

Development of greenways will often encounter physical barriers.

Greenways may encounter difficulties with landscape and manmade elements of the environment such as major roads, railroads and residential/commercial developments in the process of development.(Ryan et al, 2004).

Greenways are also susceptible to changes in land use and their continuity can easily be broken by development for roads, housing, industry or other transport schemes (Cooper and Hull 1979; Grimshaw 1982, quoted in Groome 1990).

The most obvious way to overcome this challenge is to propose greenways in landscapes that are free from physical barriers. Areas that are free of physical barriers are more likely to have the potential for greenway development and likely to need less funding. To make further areas

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available for such use will require funding and innovative bypass type planning to overcome the physical barriers.

6.4 METHODOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS

To acquire the best results, the research employed a descriptive that incorporated quantitative methods of data collection together with statistical techniques for establishing relationship. The research used a large scale study samples of 92 and due to time limitations, quantitative methods were used majorly because of its aspect of positivism.

This study therefore is based on the following-

- Facts and general rules that have enabled prediction of behaviour
- Analysis of deductions
- Methodology functioning on the adoption of natural science where objectivity is valued.

- Separation of object and subject. The researcher only “interact” within their objects of study through a medium e.g. a questionnaire.

6.5 GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

The ability to handle the existing conflicts between different neighbouring communities in a peaceful manner is the prospect of this thesis. This research only focussed on one situs which is the Bomet and Nyamira border zone whose occupants in study are the Kipsigis and Kisii communities respectively.

More contact between these communities from findings, will facilitate cohesion. If this project could be embraced by relevant authorities and be replicated elsewhere at border zones not necessary for peace initiatives but for other purposes (cultural displays, ecological conservation, recreation activities, economic activities etc.), through other ways, this effect becomes a great contribution towards achieving national cohesion with every citizen participating in the realization of the vision 2030.

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This strategy, besides aiding to achieve social cohesion, it will definitely come along with other benefits- economic, environmental,, hence proving to be a sustainability movement.

6.5.1 Open spaces and cohesion

From the literature review and findings, it is evident that open spaces are a tool for cohesion.in these open spaces, people who have actualized themselves in terms of the larger society meet and interact with other community members.

From earlier argument, we saw that people get actualized on the basis of the interpersonal ties theory in the case where their identity and values are recognized then they meet at a common platform, where all are equal in status, having a common goal. Cohesion will further be achieved in the case where it is promoted by the local authorities and contact is made pleasurable by a proper spatial design that incorporates aspects of proper landscaping, attractive features such as fountains etc.More of these guidelines are listed in the next chapters.

6.6 Policy recommendations

Spatial policy should be formulated so as to encourage integrative measures that will in turn aid to achieve cohesion. More to this, an institutional framework that enforces laws and policies on integration and cohesion should be established. Projects that encourage cohesion (educational, workshops and seminars , agricultural projects, sporting activities ,recreation activities) should be encouraged.

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6.7 Design recommendations

Open spaces in the greenway network entail (Corridors, Nodes and Patches).

Design guidelines for Corridors, Nodes and Patches in the greenway network to achieve cohesion:-

- Planning for integration should be considered.

This can be achieved through the use of components of integration such as common squares, plazas, and places that have attractive features such as monuments, water features etc. where people can form social gatherings or come to visit.

Corridors should have provision for frequent heads and access points that offer proper linkage to destinations and activity nodes using inter-connected pathways and streets.

- Improvement of aesthetics.

This aspect can be achieved by maximising on attractive colours and textures for the different elements incorporated in the landscape to improve the visual quality, maximising on borrowed views, designing regional trails for recreation and transportation following natural features and the proper landscaping of spaces and the use of attractive forms and shapes.

Figure 1 Sculpture element; a component of integration (Source; author)

Figure 2 Trails following natural features (source; author)

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- Planning for safe and secure environments. This could be achieved by provision of proper lighting systems to enhance visual acuity, and the design of wide streetscapes that prevent conflict of movement within the streets providing shade facilities at various places with grade separated crossings at major roads.
- They also should incorporate principles of sustainability and hence should be places where the needs of people.(recreational, educational, economic etc.)can be met.
- Besides improving the aesthetics, properly designing to enhance cohesion, having the components of the greenway network functional and other provisions stated, the principles of equality, equity and inter-connectivity should be considered to allow for the representation of all its users, redistribution in terms of allocations within the greenway network so that all its users feel recognised.

Figure3. Planning for safe environments

Figure 4.sustainability capabilities

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- They should be functional, having activities that give identity to communities of interest e.g. road shows.

6.8 Area For further research

This thesis, though comprehensive it may be, further studies could be carried out in other specific types of greenway networks especially ecological greenways which ought to be considered by planners due to the devastating decline of greenery and massive urbanisation. (Rob H. G. Jongman, Gloria Pungetti. Ecological Networks and Greenways: Concept, Design, Implementation.)

Figure 5. Functional spaces (source; author)

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SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE AND BUILDING SCIENCES

DEPARTMENT OF LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE

APPENDIX 1. SAMPLE QUESTIONNAIRE(Pilot study)

CONFIDENTIAL: The information provided in this survey shall be used for academic purposes only

Key to scale: 1= Extremely good, 2= Good, 3=Not sure, 4=Fair, 5= Poor

OPEN SPACES

A.SPATIAL ATTRIBUTES

1. How would you best rate the status of the green space planning in the area in terms of;-

	1	2	3	4	5
VISUAL QUALITY	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
SAFETY/SECURITY	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]

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CONNECTIVITY TO DIFFERENT LAND USES	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
SUSTAINABILITY	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
STREET WIDTH	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
TRAFFIC VOLUMES	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
VEGETATION CANOPY	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]

II. How could any of the above attribute be linked to cohesion in the area?.....

.....

III. Describe the kind of weather pattern in the area.

.....

B.TYPOLOGY *(Tick inside the bracket where appropriate)*

I. What open space typologies are found in your county?

- | | | |
|------------------------------|---|---|
| Parks and gardens | Natural and semi-natural green spaces [] , | Provision for Children and Adults [] , |
| Amenity green space [] , | Outdoor sport facility [] , | Allotments [] , |
| Church yards [] , | Civic spaces [] , | Green corridors [] , |
| Farmland and farm tracks [] | | |

Others

II. What is your opinion about the quality of the typology found in your county?

TYPOLOGY	QUALITY				
1.....	1[]	2[]	3[]	4[]	5[]
2.....	1[]	2[]	3[]	4[]	5[]
3.....	1[]	2[]	3[]	4[]	5[]
4.....	1[]	2[]	3[]	4[]	5[]

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5..... 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

Others.....

III. Do you ever visit any of these typologies? [] yes [] no

iv. If yes for what reasons do you visit them?.....

V. Do you find other people who have also come to visit? [] yes [] no

VI. If yes how many people approximately? [] 1-10, [] 11-30, [] 31-50, [] >50

VI. Which category of people are the majority? [] Children, [] Youths, [] Adults

VII. Based on your opinion,how would you best rate the importance of these typologies in terms of-

Functionality 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

Economical 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

Interaction with members of your community 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

Interaction with the members of Kisii/Kipsigis 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

C. COHESION

COHESION BETWEEN BOMET AND NYAMIRA COUNTIES

a) What is the state of cohesion;

I.Within your community? 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

II.Between your community and the neighbouring community of Kisii/Kipsigis?

1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

b) What factors affect social cohesion between the Kipsigis and Kisii ethnic groups found in this area?

Political factors [] Economic factors [] Cultural factors [] Land Issues []

Others (Please specify).....

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c) What is the main type of conflict in this area?

Inter-ethnic (without) [] Intra-ethnic (within) [] Multi-ethnic []

IDENTITY AND COMMON VALUES

d) List 5 outdoor activities / ceremonies that give identity to your community

SOCIO-ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES CULTURAL ACTIVITIES CEREMONIES

Others (Please specify)

e) How often do these activities and ceremonies occur?

Weekly [] Monthly [] Annually [] Every 2-4 years []

Others (Please specify)..... For what reasons do you conduct these activities?

Cultural reasons [] Religious beliefs [] Recreation purposes [] Socialization purposes []

Others (Please specify).....

f) Where are these activities conducted specifically?.....

g) How do you find these activities and ceremonies?

Educative [] Involving [] Interactive [] Enjoyable []

Others (Please specify).....

f) Are there restrictions as to the attendees?

Yes [] No []

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SOCIAL NETWORKS

g) What common activities/ceremonies bring your community together with the neighbouring community group of Kisii or Kipsigis?

SOCIO-ECONOMIC
ACTIVITIES

CULTURAL ACTIVITIES

CEREMONIES

Others (Please specify).....

h) Who conducts these activities?

Youths [] Family Heads [] Elders [] Clan heads []

i) How often do you come together?

Weekly [] Monthly [] Annually [] Every 2-4 years []

j) What projects and programmes would be effective to enhance interaction between the Kisii and the Kipsigis communities of Nyamira and Bomet Counties respectively?.

k) How often do conflicts between the Kipsigis and Kisii occur?

Weekly [] Monthly [] Annually [] every 2-5yrs [] over 6yrs []

l) What are the effects of the conflicts in the area?

Loss of lives [] Loss of animals [] Loss of Property []

Others (Please specify).....

m) Who gets involved in solving dispute in times of conflict?

Youths [] Family heads [] Clan heads [] Elders [] The Government Of Kenya [] NGOs []

n) In what ways have the conflicts affected the physical environment?

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

BIODATA

GENDER: Male [] Female []

AGE: 13-20yrs [] s > 20≤30yrs [] >30≤45yrs [] >45≤60yrs [] >60 yrs []

NATIONALITY: Kenyan [] Other []

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND: Primary [] Secondary [] Tertiary []

Others please indicate.....

.....

OCCUPATION: Student [] Level..... Employed [] Non-employed [] Self-employed [] Other.....

RESIDENCE: BOMET COUNTY [] NYAMIRA COUNTY []

Others please indicate.....

.....

Number of years as a resident.....

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Appendix 2 SAMPLE INTERVIEW SCHEDULE (Actual data collection)

CONFIDENTIAL: The information provided in this survey shall be used for academic purposes only.

INSTRUCTION: Please respond to all questions and tick as appropriately.

1. Describe the status of the relationship between the ethnic groups of Bomet and Nyamira counties
2. What is the status of the greenspace planning between Nyamira and Bomet counties?
3. What are some of the activities that bring the two communities together?
4. What causes conflict between these two groups?

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5. Explain the methods that were used to solve the conflicts.
6. Describe the effects of conflicts to both communities and their resultative effect on the landscape?
7. Where do most people in both communities prefer spending time for socialization purposes?
8. Would the establishment of a greenway network between the two communities enhance social integration?
9. What spatial strategies, programmes and projects if included in the greenway network design would result to the ultimate integration of these two communities?

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APPENDIX 3 SAMPLE QUESTIONNAIRE(Actual data collection)

THIS QUESTIONNAIRE WILL BE USED FOR CONFIDENTIAL PURPOSES ONLY.

A.OPEN SPACES

INSTRUCTIONS-*TICK INSIDE THE BRACKETS WHERE*
1[] IS EXTREMELY GOOD, 2[] IS GOOD, 3[] IS NOT SURE
4[] IS FAIR AND 5[] IS POOR

1) How do you appreciate the following in terms of -;

- VISUAL QUALITY

Beauty 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

Shape/form 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

Colour 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

Texture Rough() Smooth()

- FUNCTIONALITY 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

- INTERACTION WITH MEMBERS
OF YOUR COMMUNITY 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]
- INTERACTION WITH MEMBERS
OF OTHER COMMUNITIES 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]
- ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES.....
.....

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2) For what purpose do you visit the area?

1

2

3

4

Which category of people who also have visited are the majority?

Male () Female ()

Age: 13-20 yrs. [] >20≤30yrs [] >30≤45yrs[]

>45≤60yrs[] >60yrs[]

3) What language is spoken most frequently used in this place?.....

4) List down places where by you prefer spending time for socialization in order of priorities.

PLACE	REASON

5) How do you find interactions -:

1. With members of your community. 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]
2. With members of the other communities. 1[] 2[] 3[] 4[] 5[]

6) How often do you interact -:

1. With members of your community.....
2. With members of the other communities.
.....

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Have you ever witnessed any case of conflict with members of your community or another community?..... If so, where did it occur?.....

7) What was the cause of the conflict?.....

.....

B.COHESSION

- IDENTITY AND COMMON VALUES

In the table below, list down 5 major activities/ceremonies that give identity to your community, the frequency (Daily, Weekly, Monthly, Annually, Undefined) within which they occur and place where they are conducted in.

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	PLACE
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		

Who takes part in these activities? Individuals [], Groups[]

Do you take part in these activities?.....

Do you meet with new people from other communities?..... if so, from which community are they?.....

.....

- SOCIAL NETWORKS

List down the most common activities that bring your community with members of other communities, the frequency and places where these activities are conducted in.

ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY	PLACE

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

BIODATA

GENDER: Male [] Female []

AGE: 13-20 yrs [] >20≤30yrs [] >30≤45yrs [] >45≤60yrs []
>60yrs []

NATIONALITY: Kenyan [] East African Region
Other.....

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND: Primary [] Secondary []
Tertiary []
Others please indicate.....

OCCUPATION:-Student []Level..... Employed[]
Non-employed [] Self employed [] Others.....

RESIDENT :BOMET COUNTY..... NYAMIRA COUNTY..... Others

please indicate.....

NUMBER OF YEARS AS A RESIDENT.....

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Appendix 4 SAMPLE INTERVIEW SCHEDULE (Actual Data collection)

1. How would you best describe the social interaction between the Kipsigis and the Kisii communities?
2. How would you best describe the security of users at the area between Bomet and Nyamira counties?
3. Does the planning in the area corporate principles of integration?
4. How do you appreciate the visual quality of this area? Are there adequate open spaces and facilities? both soft and hard spaces?
5. What aspects of the soft landscapes have meaning to people in this county?
6. What among these aspects have activities or activities tied to them?
7. Do the open spaces corporate components of integration?
8. Do you think the local authorities have endeavoured to develop spaces for social interactions in this area? What would you suggest?
9. What projects and programmes do you think could be used as tools to foster interactions between the two communities?

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OBSERVATION CHECKLIST

NUMBER

PLACE

OBSERVATION

LANDSCAPE ELEMENTS

THE POTENTIAL OF GREENWAY NETWORK STRATEGY IN LINKING COUNTIES FOR SOCIAL COHESION

Map from Survey Offices ,Bomet